

New AIR indicator based on POD_Y – proposal of its part related to crops

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Summary

Ground-level ozone (O_3) is considered the most damaging common air pollutant to vegetation, negatively impacting ecosystems, crop yields and forest health. O_3 enters plant leaves through stomata and reacts rapidly in intercellular spaces.

The European air quality standard for vegetation protection, as defined in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU, 2024), is based on O_3 indicator AOT40, which is the accumulated O_3 concentration over $80 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in a given period. Annually, the European Environmental Agency (EEA) prepares and publishes the AQ indicator *AIR004 – Exposure of European’s ecosystem to ozone* (EEA, 2025b). This indicator is based on the AOT40 metrics, and more specifically, on the AOT40 maps prepared by the ETC HE (Horálek et al., 2024). It consists of two parts, i.e. the exposure to ozone of agricultural areas (based on the AOT40 for vegetation) and of forested areas (based on the AOT40 for forests).

Although widely used, AOT40 is not biologically optimal for assessing O_3 risk, as it does not consider stomatal uptake or any environmental factors affecting the O_3 uptake via stomata. It is widely acknowledged that O_3 -induced damage is more closely related to stomatal uptake than to ambient concentrations. Consequently, a flux-based metric such as Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_Y), which quantifies the accumulated stomatal O_3 flux above a threshold Y , provides a more accurate measure of O_3 exposure than AOT40.

This report proposes a new indicator based on POD_Y as complementary information to the current EEA indicator *AIR004*. Similarly to the *AIR004*, the new POD_Y -based indicator should also show the O_3 exposure of crops and forests separately. This report develops the first part of the new indicator, which is related to the flux-related O_3 exposure of crops. The flux-related O_3 exposure of forest trees is planned to be developed in 2026.

Two options of the new indicator related to the crops are considered, i.e. the crop specific POD_Y indicator and a more generic metric based on the POD_Y used in the Integrated Assessment Modelling (i.e. POD_YIAM), which can be applied for different crops. The advantage of the crop specific POD_Y metric is in its more exact estimation of the O_3 impacts on the corresponding crop, however, it should be applied only to areas covered by this specific crop. On the other hand, the POD_YIAM is more suitable for estimating the O_3 impacts on the wide variety of crops, and thus it can be applied to areas covered by crops in general. For this reason, the metric POD_3IAM for crops is recommended to be used in the POD_Y -based indicator for crops.

In this report, the POD_3IAM for crops is applied as a basic option for this new indicator. Its results for 2022 and 2023 are presented and analysed. Additionally, as an alternative option, the crop specific metrics POD_6 for wheat and potato are also applied. Subsequently, the results of these two options are compared mutually and with the current *AIR004* indicator based on the AOT40 for vegetation metric. Based on the results and their analysis, it is concluded that the new AIR indicator based on POD_Y should complement the current *AIR004* indicator, not substitute it. Apart from that, it is concluded that the new indicator based on the POD_3IAM for crops can be fairly used to represent different crop species.

In addition, the reasons for the POD_Y levels and inter-annual differences have been analysed and discussed for POD_Y for wheat, as a case study. It seems that phenology and temperature and also soil moisture in water-limited regions of Europe play a major role in the POD_Y levels, together with the O_3 concentrations.

1 Introduction

Ground-level ozone (referred to as O₃) is a secondary photochemical pollutant formed in complex chain reactions from precursors such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), carbon monoxide (CO), and methane (CH₄). These precursors originate from both natural and anthropogenic sources (Fowler et al., 2008; Anav et al., 2016; Nolle et al., 2002). Since O₃ formation depends on meteorological conditions, its levels fluctuate considerably from year to year (Cox and Chu, 1993; Jacob et al., 1993). As a photochemical pollutant, its presence in the atmosphere is closely linked to solar radiation and high temperatures, which drive its formation (Jacob and Winner, 2009; Coates et al., 2016).

O₃ is considered to be the most damaging common air pollutant to vegetation, negatively impacting crop yields and forest health (Ashmore, 2005; Cieslik, 2009; Fares et al., 2017; EEA, 2020). O₃-induced damage occurs at multiple biological levels, from individual cells and leaves to whole organisms and ecosystems (Fuhrer, 2002; Ashmore, 2005; Ainsworth, 2016; Emberson et al., 2018; Mills et al., 2018). Additionally, elevated O₃ concentrations threaten terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystem services (Mills et al., 2018; Agathokleous et al., 2020; Reif et al., 2023).

O₃ enters plant leaves through stomata and reacts rapidly in intercellular spaces (Fares et al., 2017). Inside the leaf, O₃ diffuses into the apoplast and decomposes into reactive oxygen species (Pell et al., 1997; Schraudner et al., 1997; Mittler, 2002). If a plant's antioxidative system is insufficient, biochemical and physiological changes occur (Ashmore, 2003; Heath, 2008; Fares et al., 2013; Emberson et al., 2018).

The European air quality standard for vegetation protection, as defined in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU, 2024), is based on the accumulated O₃ concentration over a threshold of 40 ppb (AOT40). More precisely, AOT40 is the sum of the difference between hourly concentrations greater than 80 µg/m³ (= 40 parts per billion) and 80 µg/m³ over a given period using only the one-hour values measured between 8.00 and 20.00 Central European Time (CET) each day, to reflect stomatal activity (Anav et al., 2016). The vegetation period covers April-September for forests and May-July for crops and other vegetation. Note that in EU (2024), only the AOT40 for vegetation (and therefore the period May-July) is considered.

Although widely used, AOT40 is not biologically optimal for assessing O₃ risk, as it does not consider stomatal uptake or any environmental factors affecting the O₃ uptake via stomata (Anav et al., 2016). The stomatal O₃ flux approach, in contrast, accounts for the actual O₃ dose entering the leaf via stomata and factors in key environmental conditions such as phenology, air temperature, soil moisture, vapour pressure deficit (VPD), and solar radiation (Emberson et al., 2000a). High ambient O₃ levels do not necessarily harm plants if stomata are closed due to unfavourable conditions, i.e. high vapour pressure deficit, high temperature and low soil humidity (Paoletti, 2006; Agyei, 2020; Ronan et al., 2020), while lower O₃ concentrations can still cause significant damage when stomata are open (Matyssek et al., 2007; Karlsson et al., 2017).

Thus, scientific consensus suggests that O₃-induced damage is more closely related to stomatal uptake than to ambient concentration (Reich, 1987; Ashmore et al., 2004; Mills et al., 2011). Consequently, a flux-based metric such as Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_y), which quantifies the accumulated stomatal O₃ flux above a threshold Y, provides a more accurate measure of O₃ exposure than AOT40 (Musselman and Massman, 1998; Nussbaum et al., 2003; Fares et al., 2010; Musselman et al., 2006; Matyssek et al., 2007; Cieslik, 2009). POD_y has been adopted in the Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP, 2017a; Mills et al., 2011) as a preferred metric. As research advances, further refinement of POD_y-based metrics will enhance our understanding of O₃ impacts on vegetation and improve mitigation strategies.

Under the European Topic Centres (ETCs, i.e. ETC HE and the previous consortia), the European wide annual air quality (AQ) maps have been routinely constructed since 2005, including the AOT40 maps (Horálek et al., 2024 and references therein). Since 2019, POD_V maps have also been prepared for different species.

Annually, the European Environmental Agency (EEA) prepares and publishes the AQ indicator *AIR004 – Exposure of European’s ecosystem to ozone* (EEA, 2025b). This indicator is based on the AOT40 metrics, and more specifically, on the AOT40 maps prepared by the ETC HE. It consists of two parts, i.e. the exposure to ozone of agricultural areas (based on the AOT40 for vegetation) and of forested areas (based on the AOT40 for forests).

This report aims to propose a new indicator based on POD_V as complementary information to the current indicator AIR004. It seems to be appropriate for this POD_V -based supplementary indicator to consist also of two parts, i.e. one related to the crops and one related to the forests. This report develops the indicator related to the crops, as a first step. The indicator related to the forests (i.e. the second half of the POD_V -based indicator) will be developed in 2026.

Two options of the new indicator related to the crops are considered, i.e. the crop specific POD_V indicator and a more generic metric based on the POD_V used in the Integrated Assessment Modelling (IAM). Next to the proposal of the indicator, the first results of this indicator for years 2022 and 2023 are presented and analysed.

POD_V is a complex indicator, which depends on different variables. As previously stated, high ambient O_3 concentrations do not necessarily lead to high POD_V values (for instance, if stomata are closed during unfavourable environmental conditions). Conversely, quite low O_3 concentrations can still lead to fairly high O_3 fluxes when stomata are open under favourable environmental conditions. For that reason, the POD_V levels and inter-annual differences are in general difficult to be understood. However, if the indicator based on the POD_V metrics is introduced, the explanation of its levels and inter-annual changes would be important. Thus, this report tries to analyse and discuss the levels and inter-annual differences of POD_6 for wheat (as a case study), in addition to the introduction of the new POD_V -based indicator.

Chapter 2 discusses two different options for the new POD_V indicator. Chapter 3 presents the results of the new indicator for 2022 and 2023 for the two discussed options. Chapter 4 compares the results of the two options of the new indicator with the current AIR004 indicator. Chapter 5 analyses the reasons for the POD_V levels and inter-annual differences. Chapter 6 gives conclusions. Annex 1 explains the methodology, while Annex 2 presents the data used. Annex 3 provides additional results of the POD_V analysis (as introduced in Chapter 5) at the level of biogeographical regions.

2 Considerations on the new POD_{γ} -based indicator

The current EEA indicator *AIR004 – Exposure of Europe’s ecosystem to ozone* (EEA, 2025b) consists of two parts, i.e. (i) Exposure of agricultural areas to ozone and (ii) Exposure of forest areas to ozone. The indicator presents two figures (Figures 2.1 and 2.2), which show the exposure of agricultural and forested areas to different values (in terms of limited number of concentration classes) of the ozone indicators AOT40 for vegetation and AOT40 for forests, respectively.

Figure 2.1 Indicator AIR004, Exposure of agricultural areas to ozone in EEA member countries

Source: EEA, 2025b

Figure 2.2 Indicator AIR004, Exposure of forest areas to ozone in EEA member countries

Source: EEA, 2025b

For the agricultural areas exposure estimation, the areas labelled as the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) level-1 class 2 “Agricultural areas” (encompassing the level-2 classes 2.1 “Arable land”, 2.2 “Permanent crops”, 2.3 “Pastures” and 2.4 “Heterogeneous agricultural areas”) are used, while the areas labelled as the CLC level-2 class 3.1 “Forests” are used for the forested areas exposure estimates. The data are presented for a time series starting in 2000 and 2005 for agricultural and forested areas, respectively.

For the exposure of agricultural areas to O₃, four concentration classes of AOT40 for vegetation are used, being the highest one that above the target value (TV) of 18 000 µg/m³, as set by the EU Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU, 2024); and the lowest one that below the long-term objective (LTO) of 6 000 µg/m³, as set by the same EU directives. For the exposure of forest areas to O₃, five concentration classes of AOT40 for forests are used, with the lowest being that one below the critical level (CL) of 10 000 µg/m³ as established by CLRTAP (2024).

As mentioned in the introductory chapter, the O₃-induced effects on vegetation are more closely related to O₃ stomatal uptake than to O₃ ambient concentration. Consequently, the flux-based POD_Y metrics are preferred in risk assessment over the concentration-based AOT40 ones. Thus, it is suggested to complement the current AIR004 indicator with the new indicator based on POD_Y.

Similarly to the current AIR004 indicator, the new POD_Y-based indicator should also show the O₃ exposure of crops and forests separately. This report concentrates on the flux-related O₃ exposure of the crops. The flux-related O₃ exposure of forest trees is planned to be assessed in 2026.

The cumulative stomatal O₃ flux through the stomata of leaves found at the top of the canopy is calculated over the course of the growing season based on ambient O₃ concentration and stomatal conductance to O₃. POD_Y is the accumulated plant uptake (flux) of O₃ above a threshold of Y during a specified time or growth period. Several POD_Y metrics exist (2024), see Box 1. As research advances, further refinement of POD_Y-based metrics will enhance our understanding of O₃ impacts on vegetation and improve mitigation strategies.

Box 1 Metrics for stomatal flux-based critical levels for POD_Y calculation

POD_YSPEC is a species-specific metric that requires extensive input data and is suitable for detailed risk assessment. It represents the phytotoxic O₃ dose above a flux threshold of Y nmol/m² PLA per second for a specific plant species or group of species, accumulated over a defined period during daylight hours. Here, PLA stands for Projected Leaf Area, i.e. the total area of the sides of the leaves that are projected towards the sun.

For crops such as wheat and potato, the Y value is set at 6 nmol/m² PLA per second, as recommended by CLRTAP (2024). The species-specific flux models and associated response functions and critical levels for O₃ sensitive crops and cultivars can be used to quantify the potential negative impacts of O₃ on the security of food supplies at the local and regional scale. They can be used to estimate yield losses, including economic losses. A flux threshold of 6 nmol/m² PLA per second (POD₆SPEC) provides the strongest flux-effect relationships for crops (Pleijel et al., 2007). O₃ effects have been shown to be significant at a 5% reduction of the effect parameter (Mills et al., 2011; Grunhage et al., 2012), forming the basis for determining critical levels (CL) for yield, weight, or quality of grain, tubers, and fruit.

POD_YIAM represents the phytotoxic O₃ dose exceeding a flux threshold of Y nmol/m² PLA per second for a specific vegetation type (like crops and forest trees), designed for large-scale modelling applications such as integrated assessment. It is a vegetation-type-specific metric with lower data requirements, making it well-suited for large-scale modelling and integrated risk assessment. POD_YIAM simplifies stomatal O₃ flux modelling by incorporating species-independent parameters. Despite these simplifications, it remains a robust tool for assessing O₃ risks at regional and global scales.

Source: CLRTAP, 2024

As presented in Box 1, the choice between $POD_{\gamma}SPEC$ and $POD_{\gamma}IAM$ depends on data availability and assessment scale, with $POD_{\gamma}SPEC$ offering high-resolution insights and $POD_{\gamma}IAM$ enabling broader applicability.

For the new POD_{γ} -based indicator related to the crops, either a crop specific $POD_{\gamma}SPEC$ metric can be used or a more generic metric $POD_{\gamma}IAM$. If the crop specific $POD_{\gamma}SPEC$ is considered, POD_6SPEC for wheat might be used, considering wheat as the most representative crop in Europe, potentially supplemented with the POD_6SPEC for potato, considering potato as a representative of the horticultural crops (without regard to its limitations regarding its applicability for the Mediterranean region, for which tomato would be more representative – however, joint use of two different crops for different areas in one European-wide indicator would be quite demanding). If a more generic $POD_{\gamma}IAM$ is considered, the POD_3IAM for crops can be applied.

The advantage of the crop specific POD_6SPEC metrics is in its more exact estimation of the O_3 impacts on the corresponding crop (wheat or potato). On the other side, the POD_3IAM is probably more suitable for estimating the potential risk of O_3 impacts on the wide variety of crops. Specifically, the POD_6SPEC for wheat and potato (labelled further simply as POD_6 for wheat and potato) should be applied only to areas covered by wheat and potato, respectively. While the POD_3IAM for crops can be applied to areas covered by crops in general.

Further, the POD_3IAM for crops application for the same agricultural areas as for which is applied the current AIR004 indicator (see above) is considered. However, its applicability for pastures (i.e. areas of CLC level-2 class 2.3) should be examined in the future, i.e. whether the use of risk indicators specific for pastures does not lead into a considerable change in areas under the risk of O_3 negative effects.

Based on the above-mentioned facts, the POD_3IAM is further examined for crops as a basic option to be used in the POD_{γ} -based indicator for crops. The reason is that it can be applied for the same agricultural area as the current AIR004 indicator (with a potential exception for pastures, see above). As an alternative option, the POD_6 for wheat and potato are examined.

3 POD_Y-based indicator related to crops – 2022 and 2023 results

In this chapter, the results of the new POD_Y-based indicator are presented (i.e. its part related to crops) for years 2022 and 2023. Based on the considerations of Chapter 2, the generic metric POD₃IAM for crops is applied as a basic option for this new indicator. Additionally, as an alternative option, the crop specific metrics POD₆ for wheat and potato are also applied.

All POD_Y metrics applied (i.e. POD₃IAM for crops, POD₆ for wheat and POD₆ for potato) have been calculated using the methodology described in CLRTAP (2024), see Annex 1. Specifically, the hourly averaged stomatal O₃ fluxes (F_{sto}) in excess of a Y threshold have been accumulated over a species or vegetation-specific accumulation period, in order to get the phytotoxic O₃ dose above the threshold Y (POD_Y). The stomatal O₃ fluxes (F_{sto}) have been calculated based on the O₃ concentration at the top of the canopy and stomatal conductance (g_{sto}) to O₃. The stomatal conductance (g_{sto}) has been calculated using a multiplicative stomatal conductance model (Emberson et al., 2000a) based on Jarvis (1976) as a function of species-specific maximum g_{sto} (expressed on a projected leaf-area basis), phenology, and prevailing environmental conditions (photosynthetic photon flux density, PPFD), air temperature, vapour pressure deficit (VPD), and soil moisture. The O₃ concentration at the top of the canopy have been calculated based on the ambient O₃ concentrations at the height of the O₃ station measurements, the aerodynamic resistance between the heights of the station measurements and the top of the canopy, the resistance to O₃ diffusion in the laminar sub-layer and other resistances. The ambient O₃ concentrations have been calculated based on O₃ measurement data, O₃ chemical transport modelling (CTM) data, surface solar radiation data and altitude. For details on the methodology and the data used, see Annex 1 and Annex 2, respectively, and Horálek et al. (2024, 2025).

O₃ effects proved to be significant at a 5 % reduction of the effect parameter (Mills et al., 2011), hence critical levels (CL) were determined for this 5 % reduction of the effect parameter (i.e. yield, weight or quality of grain), based on the slope of the function. For CLs as set by CLRTAP, see Annex 1, Table A1.2.

For POD₆ for wheat and potato for 2022 and 2023, the routine spatial maps of these indicators as prepared for Horálek et al. (2024, 2025) have been used. The maps of POD₃IAM for crops have been calculated under the ETC HE for the first time. All maps have been constructed in 0.1° resolution and further converted to 2 km resolution. The maps have been created using the monitoring data from the rural background stations only, based on the assumption there are no areas covered by crop species in urban areas.

The basic option of the new POD_Y-based indicator using the POD₃IAM is presented in Section 3.1. The alternative option of the indicator using the POD₆ for wheat and potato is presented in Section 3.2.

3.1 Basic option: Indicator using generic metric POD₃IAM for crops

At first, the maps of the POD₃IAM for crops have been constructed. Maps 3.1 and 3.2 present the spatial distribution of POD₃IAM for crops in 2022 and 2023. The areas with POD₃IAM for crops values below the CL for crops established by CLRTAP (2024) (i.e. 7.9 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in green.

One can see that in most areas, especially those above the CL, the POD₃IAM for crops maps show higher values in 2023 than in 2022 (see also Map 4.1, upper right).

In order to estimate the exposure of crops to O₃ in terms of POD₃IAM, the rural maps of POD₃IAM for crops have been combined with the land cover CLC2018 map in 100 m resolution (EU, 2020). The same agricultural areas as in the current AIR004 indicator have been used, i.e. the areas labelled as the CLC level-1 class 2 “Agricultural areas” (encompassing the level-2 classes 2.1 “Arable land”, 2.2 “Permanent crops”, 2.3 “Pastures” and 2.4 “Heterogeneous agricultural areas”).

Map 3.1 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose – POD₃IAM for crops, rural map, 2022. To be applied only for areas covered by crop species

Map 3.2 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose – POD₃IAM for crops, rural map, 2023. To be applied only for areas covered by crop species

Tables 3.1 and 3.2 present the exposure of crops to O₃ in terms of POD₃IAM for crops for 2022 and 2023, respectively. The tables show the frequency distribution of the agricultural area over some exposure classes for each country, for EU-27, EEA-32, EEA-38 and the total mapping area (with and without Türkiye in the last three cases) and for five large European regions (see Annex 1, Section A1.4). In addition, the absolute and relative agricultural areas where POD₃IAM for crops values are above the CL threshold are presented, as well as the agricultural area weighted concentrations, i.e. the average POD₃IAM values across the agricultural areas.

Table 3.1 Exposure of crops to O₃ and agricultural area weighted concentrations, O₃ indicator POD₃IAM for crops, 2022

Country	Agricultural area, 2022			Fraction of agricultural area, 2022 (%)					Agricultural-weighted POD ₃ IAM, 2022 (mmol/m ² PLA)
	Total area (km ²)	> CL for crops (7.9 mmol/m ² PLA)		< 7.9	7.9-16	16-24	24-32	> 32	
		(km ²)	(%)						
Albania	7,709	6,779	87.9	12.1	22.4	22.8	25.6	17.2	20.8
Andorra	13	13	100.0		38.4	59.9	1.8		17.4
Austria	26,827	21,670	80.8	19.2	12.3	10.2	32.8	25.5	22.7
Belgium	17,396	15,321	88.1	11.9	25.0	12.8	34.9	15.3	21.1
Bosnia and Herzegovina	17,021	16,224	95.3	4.7	42.1	44.9	8.4		16.8
Bulgaria	57,021	49,562	86.9	13.1	31.1	36.0	19.2	0.6	16.8
Croatia	20,886	19,428	93.0	7.0	37.6	36.8	14.6	4.0	16.8
Cyprus	3,697	588	15.9	84.1	15.9				2.9
Czechia	44,784	43,696	97.6	2.4	16.8	16.8	31.8	32.2	25.7
Denmark	25,671	18,304	71.3	28.7	8.0	37.0	24.8	1.5	13.6
Estonia	13,495	7,506	55.6	44.4	31.0	24.6			9.5
Finland	26,472	25,173	95.1	4.9	81.6	13.4			11.7
France	318,886	309,564	97.1	2.9	18.2	22.2	30.6	26.1	24.4
Germany	201,436	185,320	92.0	8.0	12.8	14.0	51.3	13.9	23.9
Greece	42,934	27,680	64.5	35.5	34.6	15.0	12.4	2.5	11.1
Hungary	60,220	45,004	74.7	25.3	33.0	25.4	5.2	11.1	14.9
Iceland	1,909	0	0.0	100.0					0.5
Ireland	43,268	33,903	78.4	21.6	78.3	0.0			9.2
Italy	148,113	123,454	83.4	16.6	29.1	14.3	19.5	20.4	19.3
Latvia	25,046	22,839	91.2	8.8	76.4	14.8			12.6
Liechtenstein	37	37	100.0		77.6	22.4			14.9
Lithuania	37,303	36,000	96.5	3.5	47.4	49.1			15.3
Luxembourg	1,351	1,268	93.8	6.2	26.8	22.3	21.8	23.0	22.3
Malta	44	0	0.0	100.0					0.3
Monaco	0	0	0.0						
Montenegro	2,179	1,786	82.0	18.0	48.8	32.8	0.2	0.2	12.5
Netherlands	22,509	19,704	87.5	12.5	13.1	13.1	35.6	25.7	22.4
North Macedonia	9,146	7,035	76.9	23.1	20.3	47.8	8.8		15.7
Norway	12,593	4,382	34.8	65.2	30.9	3.9			5.5
Poland	181,630	146,666	80.7	19.3	14.4	33.1	28.7	4.5	18.5
Portugal	41,721	28,425	68.1	31.9	21.6	11.5	13.2	21.9	17.1
Romania	133,738	118,059	88.3	11.7	43.8	32.7	11.7	0.0	15.2
San Marino	42	42	100.0		44.9	51.2	3.9		15.8
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	46,768	37,848	100.0	19.1	28.7	21.9	26.8	3.5	17.1
Slovakia	23,015	18,048	78.4	21.6	63.1	12.6	2.4	0.4	11.4
Slovenia	6,942	6,910	99.5	0.5	1.1	47.5	33.2	17.7	25.1
Spain	237,726	150,683	63.4	36.6	29.2	12.6	13.4	8.2	13.7
Sweden	36,217	10,682	29.5	70.5	20.7	4.5	4.3		4.7
Switzerland	11,359	10,702	94.2	5.8	13.3	26.0	48.5	6.3	23.0
Türkiye	330,826	93,754	28.3	71.7	22.9	3.5	0.7	1.2	6.8
Total	2,237,952	1,664,061	74.4	25.6	26.7	18.4	19.2	10.1	16.1
Total without Türkiye	1,907,126	1,570,307	82.3	17.7	27.3	20.9	22.4	11.7	17.7
EEA-38	2,237,897	1,664,006	74.4	25.6	26.7	18.4	19.2	10.1	16.1
EEA-38 without Türkiye	1,907,070	1,570,252	82.3	17.7	27.3	20.9	22.4	11.7	17.7
EEA-32	2,155,074	1,594,333	74.0	26.0	26.5	17.9	19.2	10.4	16.4
EEA-32 without Türkiye	1,824,248	1,500,579	82.3	17.7	27.2	20.5	22.5	12.0	18.1
EU-27	1,798,337	1,485,458	82.6	17.4	27.3	20.6	22.5	12.2	18.2
Northern Europe	178,706	124,886	69.9	30.1	42.6	22.7	4.4	0.2	10.6
Western Europe	337,268	319,957	94.9	5.1	24.7	16.2	28.8	25.2	22.9
Central Europe	556,252	478,054	85.9	14.1	17.8	22.1	34.2	11.9	20.7
Southern Europe	540,432	390,689	72.3	27.7	28.4	15.6	16.0	12.3	16.0
South-Eastern Europe	625,294	350,476	56.0	44.0	29.6	17.3	7.8	1.3	9.9
Kosovo	4,167	4,119	98.8	1.2	21.9	37.4	39.5	0.0	21.2
Serbia (without Kosovo)	42,601	33,728	79.2	20.8	29.4	20.3	25.6	3.8	16.7

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed agricultural area exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no agricultural area in exposure.

Table 3.2 Exposure of crops to O₃ and agricultural area weighted concentrations, O₃ indicator POD₃IAM for crops, 2023

Country	Agricultural area, 2023			Fraction of agricultural area, 2023 (%)					Agricultural-weighted POD ₃ IAM, 2023 (mmol/m ² PLA)
	Total area (km ²)	> CL for crops (7.9 mmol/m ² PLA)		< 7.9	7.9-16	16-24	24-32	> 32	
		(km ²)	(%)						
Albania	7,709	7,611	98.7	1.3	23.1	21.9	25.7	28.0	24.1
Andorra	13	13	100.0		35.5	61.7	2.8		17.4
Austria	26,827	25,743	96.0	4.0	11.2	28.0	41.5	15.3	24.3
Belgium	17,396	16,684	95.9	4.1	4.9	18.7	14.2	58.0	29.3
Bosnia and Herzegovina	17,021	16,893	99.3	0.7	24.1	45.0	29.6	0.5	19.9
Bulgaria	57,021	46,705	81.9	18.1	38.3	27.3	15.4	1.0	14.9
Croatia	20,886	20,784	99.5	0.5	6.3	36.1	46.8	10.3	23.2
Cyprus	3,697	429	11.6	88.4	10.2	1.4			1.7
Czechia	44,784	44,353	99.0	1.0	12.1	13.2	38.1	35.6	27.8
Denmark	25,671	21,127	82.3	17.7	10.9	14.3	43.1	14.1	17.9
Estonia	13,495	7,341	54.4	45.6	19.1	19.7	15.6		11.9
Finland	26,472	25,298	95.6	4.4	68.1	27.4	0.0		13.0
France	318,886	308,121	96.6	3.4	8.1	21.6	28.2	38.7	27.0
Germany	201,436	195,689	97.1	2.9	5.0	11.6	28.7	51.9	28.8
Greece	42,934	30,513	71.1	28.9	37.2	21.8	10.2	1.9	11.3
Hungary	60,220	53,127	88.2	11.8	7.7	26.1	37.1	17.3	22.9
Iceland	1,909	0	0.0	100.0					1.3
Ireland	43,268	41,164	95.1	4.9	82.3	12.8			13.2
Italy	148,113	140,246	94.7	5.3	14.7	22.2	19.6	38.3	25.4
Latvia	25,046	20,481	81.8	18.2	28.3	16.6	36.9		17.4
Liechtenstein	37	37	100.0		77.6	22.4			15.2
Lithuania	37,303	33,141	88.8	11.2	32.8	29.9	26.1		17.4
Luxembourg	1,351	1,268	93.8	6.2	5.5	34.3	12.1	41.8	25.6
Malta	44	0	0.0	100.0					0.0
Monaco	0	0							
Montenegro	2,179	2,167	99.5	0.5	55.3	39.0	5.1	0.1	14.4
Netherlands	22,509	20,801	92.4	7.6	4.9	6.0	16.6	64.9	27.7
North Macedonia	9,146	7,913	86.5	13.5	29.7	47.5	9.3		16.3
Norway	12,593	4,422	35.1	64.9	29.6	5.5			6.1
Poland	181,630	148,591	81.8	18.2	12.5	17.2	44.5	7.6	20.4
Portugal	41,721	30,106	72.2	27.8	19.9	14.6	11.6	26.1	19.5
Romania	133,738	122,363	91.5	8.5	34.3	37.7	18.3	1.2	17.3
San Marino	42	42	100.0			44.9	29.4	25.7	25.2
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	46,768	43,447	100.0	7.1	5.5	31.6	37.7	18.1	23.9
Slovakia	23,015	23,015	100.0		28.6	40.2	29.8	1.4	20.3
Slovenia	6,942	6,942	100.0		0.6	1.9	37.1	60.4	32.7
Spain	237,726	116,164	48.9	51.1	15.7	10.1	11.3	11.8	12.4
Sweden	36,217	12,751	35.2	64.8	12.7	16.0	3.7	2.8	6.9
Switzerland	11,359	10,556	92.9	7.1	12.3	28.9	50.1	1.7	22.2
Türkiye	330,826	134,577	40.7	59.3	35.9	3.8	0.7	0.2	6.8
Total	2,237,952	1,740,628	77.8	22.2	20.2	17.8	21.0	18.7	17.2
Total without Türkiye	1,907,126	1,606,050	84.2	15.8	17.5	20.3	24.5	21.9	19.5
EEA-38	2,237,897	1,740,572	77.8	22.2	20.2	17.8	21.0	18.7	17.2
EEA-38 without Türkiye	1,907,070	1,605,995	84.2	15.8	17.5	20.3	24.5	21.9	19.5
EEA-32	2,155,074	1,662,541	77.1	22.9	20.4	17.2	20.6	18.9	17.2
EEA-32 without Türkiye	1,824,248	1,527,963	83.8	16.2	17.6	19.6	24.2	22.3	19.5
EU-27	1,798,337	1,512,948	84.1	15.9	17.6	19.6	24.3	22.7	19.6
Northern Europe	178,706	124,562	69.7	30.3	28.6	19.8	18.8	2.6	13.2
Western Europe	337,268	331,122	98.2	1.8	17.4	18.7	20.1	41.9	20.4
Central Europe	556,252	508,054	91.3	8.7	9.7	17.3	36.7	27.6	24.7
Southern Europe	540,432	374,428	69.3	30.7	16.3	16.4	17.3	19.2	20.8
South-Eastern Europe	625,294	402,462	64.4	35.6	32.0	18.4	11.4	2.5	12.3
Kosovo	4,167	4,167	100.0		9.5	42.3	47.4	0.8	23.9
Serbia (without Kosovo)	42,601	39,280	92.2	7.8	5.2	30.5	36.7	19.8	23.7

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed agricultural area exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no agricultural area in exposure.

Figures 3.1 and 3.2 show the frequency distribution of the agricultural area over some O₃ exposure classes (in terms of POD₃IAM for crops) for each country, for five large European regions, for EU-27, for EEA-32 (with and without Türkiye) and for the total mapping area, for 2022 and 2023. The figures present graphically the core information of Tables 3.1 and 3.2.

Figure 3.1 Percentage of the agricultural area (%) exposed to different values of the indicator POD₃IAM for crops (mmol/m² PLA), 2022

Figure 3.2 Percentage of the agricultural area (%) exposed to different values of the indicator POD₃IAM for crops (mmol/m² PLA), 2023

The Figures 3.1 and 3.2 can be used for the new AIR indicator based on the POD_y. Specifically, the bar showing the frequency distribution for the EEA-32 can be directly used for this purpose.

3.2 Alternative option: Indicator using crop specific metrics POD₆ for wheat and potato

As an alternative option, the indicator using POD₆ for wheat and potato has been prepared. Maps 3.3 and 3.4 present the spatial distribution of POD₆ for wheat and potato in 2022 and 2023, respectively.

Map 3.3 POD_6 for wheat (left) and potato (right), rural map, 2022

Map 3.4 POD_6 for wheat (left) and potato (right), rural map, 2023

The areas with POD_6 for wheat values below the CL for grain yield (i.e. 1.3 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in green. The areas with POD_6 for wheat values in between CL for grain yield and CL for 1,000-grain weight (which is 1.5 mmol/m² PLA) and in between CL for 1,000-grain weight and CL for protein yield (which is 2 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in yellow and orange, respectively. The areas with POD_6 values for wheat above the CL for protein yield are marked in red and dark red. The areas with POD_6 for potato values below the CL for tuber yield (i.e. 3.8 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in green, while the areas with POD_6 for potato values above this threshold are marked in yellow, orange, red and dark red.

In order to estimate the exposure of wheat and potato to O₃ in terms of POD_6 for wheat and potato, respectively, the relevant rural maps of POD_6 have been combined with the area covered by wheat and potato, respectively, according to the agricultural data in 1 km resolution as applied in Schucht et al. (2024). For description of these data, see Annex 2, Section A2.3. Note that the data are less detailed (in terms of spatial resolution) compared to the CLC2018 applied for the basic variant of the new POD_Y -based indicator.

Table 3.3 presents the exposure of wheat and potato to O₃ in terms of POD_6 for wheat and potato, respectively, for the year 2022. The table shows the frequency distribution of the wheat and potato agricultural areas over some exposure classes for EU-27, EEA-32, EEA-38 and the total mapping area (with and without Türkiye in the last three cases) and for five large European regions. In addition, the wheat and potato agricultural area weighted concentrations are presented, i.e. the average values of POD_6 for wheat and potato, respectively, across the relevant agricultural areas. Table 3.4 presents the same numbers for 2023.

Table 3.3 Exposure of wheat (left) and potato (right) to O₃ and agricultural area weighted concentrations, O₃ indicators POD₆ for wheat (left) and potato (right), 2022

Country	Wheat, 2022						Potato, 2022					
	Fraction of wheat agricultural area (%)					Agr.-w. POD ₆ wheat	Fraction of potato agricultural area (%)					Agr.-w. POD ₆ potato
	< 1.3	1.3- 1.5	1.5- 2	2- 3	> 3		< 3.8	3.8- 6	6- 9	9- 12	> 12	
	(mmol/m ² PLA)						(mmol/m ² PLA)					
Albania	33.9	13.4	26.4	26.0	0.3	1.49	91.8	7.6	0.7		2.71	
Andorra				100		2.50	50.0	50.0			3.55	
Austria	18.4	1.2	3.7	11.4	65.3	3.08	38.6	38.5	22.7	0.2	4.09	
Belgium	22.6	2.4	4.7	9.4	61.0	2.89	43.0	57.0			3.65	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	47.1	18.9	23.1	11.0		1.37	96.9	3.1			2.21	
Bulgaria	24.5	3.9	17.3	42.0	12.3	1.97	71.7	25.3	3.0		2.95	
Croatia	23.4	11.0	25.3	31.1	9.1	1.84	62.4	37.2	0.4		3.29	
Cyprus	90.1	2.5	3.2	4.2		0.41	100				0.13	
Czechia	10.5	1.1	3.8	10.8	73.8	3.57	11.4	40.8	47.4	0.5	5.70	
Denmark	34.3	3.0	8.8	36.4	17.5	1.81	99.9	0.1			1.49	
Estonia	63.5	2.9	8.5	22.3	2.8	1.04	100				1.30	
Finland	57.5	6.5	17.1	17.0	1.9	1.34	100				0.61	
France	6.2	1.5	8.9	28.9	54.6	2.90	50.5	47.7	1.8	0.0	3.59	
Germany	9.8	1.5	3.7	10.8	74.1	3.22	19.6	59.2	21.2		4.85	
Greece	60.0	11.4	18.0	9.9	0.6	1.12	96.1	3.2	0.8		1.48	
Hungary	30.7	1.8	6.6	28.6	32.3	2.18	39.6	47.8	12.6		3.67	
Iceland	100					0.01	100				0.01	
Ireland	100					0.33	100				0.24	
Italy	22.9	3.1	11.8	31.1	31.0	2.40	65.2	27.1	7.3	0.4	3.10	
Latvia	79.1	9.5	8.8	2.5	0.1	0.89	100				1.08	
Liechtenstein		37.8	5.4	51.4	5.4	1.93	100				1.03	
Lithuania	52.1	23.3	22.0	2.6		1.27	100				1.70	
Luxembourg	30.7	0.5	2.3	19.5	47.0	2.47	46.0	54.0			3.68	
Malta							100				0.0	
Monaco												
Montenegro	59.8	10.7	15.0	14.5		1.15	98.9	1.1			1.75	
Netherlands	14.6	1.4	5.7	10.7	67.6	3.19	37.1	62.9			3.79	
North Macedonia	71.6	9.0	10.4	9.0	0.0	1.07	99.9	0.1			1.87	
Norway	73.8		25.0	1.3		0.67	100				0.27	
Poland	26.4	2.7	15.7	35.7	19.5	1.99	65.0	28.9	6.1		3.11	
Portugal	37.3	6.2	15.3	26.3	15.0	1.66	81.9	13.3	4.8		2.15	
Romania	32.6	6.1	22.0	37.6	1.7	1.59	68.5	31.4	0.1		2.91	
San Marino				100		2.53	75.7	24.3			3.33	
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	28.4	8.6	26.7	31.5	4.8	1.64	77.1	22.9	0.0		2.65	
Slovakia	55.5	6.0	15.5	16.6	6.5	1.27	64.4	32.1	3.4	0.0	3.01	
Slovenia	1.6		0.8	22.4	75.2	3.52	8.4	66.0	25.7		5.39	
Spain	32.5	4.9	16.1	32.3	14.2	1.78	93.3	5.9	0.7		1.70	
Sweden	88.5	1.6	4.6	2.6	2.7	0.35	100				0.25	
Switzerland	6.6	1.2	5.7	46.4	40.1	2.73	47.9	51.9	0.1		3.34	
Türkiye	84.1	4.2	7.3	3.5	0.9	0.59	98.5	0.9	0.7	0.0	0.91	
Total	39.2	4.4	11.7	21.1	23.7	1.84	71.6	23.5	4.9	0.0	2.53	
Total without Türkiye	31.0	4.4	12.5	24.3	27.8	2.07	66.7	27.5	5.7	0.0	2.82	
EEA-38	39.2	4.4	11.7	21.1	23.7	1.84	71.6	23.5	4.9	0.0	2.53	
EEA-38 without Türkiye	31.0	4.4	12.5	24.3	27.8	2.07	66.7	27.5	5.7	0.0	2.82	
EEA-32	39.1	4.0	11.2	21.0	24.7	1.86	70.8	24.0	5.2	0.0	2.53	
EEA-32 without Türkiye	30.5	4.0	11.9	24.4	29.2	2.11	65.6	28.4	6.0	0.0	2.84	
EU-27	30.6	4.0	11.9	24.3	29.2	2.10	65.7	28.2	6.1	0.1	2.84	
Northern Europe	67.8	7.1	11.6	10.6	2.9	0.98	100.0	0.0			0.82	
Western Europe	13.1	1.2	5.4	21.6	58.8	2.87	48.2	50.6	1.2		3.48	
Central Europe	20.1	2.1	8.7	22.2	46.9	2.62	39.4	44.1	16.4	0.1	4.08	
Southern Europe	30.9	4.8	15.2	30.1	19.0	1.94	81.9	14.9	3.1	0.1	2.27	
South-Eastern Europe	60.1	6.0	14.1	17.2	2.6	1.08	87.5	11.8	0.7	0.0	1.78	
Kosovo	16.1	20.2	41.5	21.2	0.9	1.69	5.2				2.87	
Serbia (without Kosovo)	30.1	7.0	24.7	32.9	5.3	1.63	25.3	0.0			2.62	

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed agricultural area exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no agricultural area in exposure.

Table 3.4 Exposure of wheat (left) and potato (right) to O₃ and agricultural area weighted concentrations, O₃ indicators POD₆ for wheat (left) and potato (right), 2023

Country	Wheat, 2023						Potato, 2023					Agr.-w. POD ₆ potato
	Fraction of wheat agricultural area (%)					Agr.-w. POD ₆ wheat	Fraction of potato agricultural area (%)					
	< 1.3	1.3-1.5	1.5-2	2-3	> 3		< 3.8	3.8-6	6-9	9-12	> 12	
	(mmol/m ² PLA)						(mmol/m ² PLA)					
Albania	76.3	9.0	12.3	2.3		0.90	95.7	4.3				1.63
Andorra				100		2.13	100					1.39
Austria	5.9	0.9	2.4	7.3	83.6	4.00	23.8	40.3	35.8			4.83
Belgium	3.0	0.2	0.2	1.7	94.8	4.42	4.3	15.8	49.9	30.0		7.66
Bosnia and Herzegovina	50.1	11.5	26.2	12.3		1.31	100					1.35
Bulgaria	22.6	5.8	36.6	34.2	0.9	1.67	99.5	0.5				1.82
Croatia	18.6	0.8	4.7	43.4	32.4	2.46	52.0	46.6	1.4			3.71
Cyprus	98.7	1.3				0.10	100					0.14
Czechia	1.0	0.2	0.2	2.4	96.2	4.33	4.7	57.4	37.9			5.69
Denmark	29.4	1.4	2.7	7.3	59.2	2.68	54.1	44.6	1.3			3.08
Estonia	63.9	1.6	4.4	23.5	6.6	1.05	97.0	3.0				1.84
Finland	84.3	3.6	7.8	4.4		0.86	100					1.29
France	6.6	1.3	3.1	11.6	77.5	3.76	15.1	23.1	46.0	15.8		6.50
Germany	4.6	0.8	2.0	5.7	86.9	4.16	8.7	17.5	70.0	3.7		6.56
Greece	99.2	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.44	96.2	3.7	0.2			1.58
Hungary	11.4	0.9	1.5	31.2	54.9	2.88	23.1	74.4	2.6			4.11
Iceland	100					0.06	100					0.00
Ireland	27.4	5.3	56.3	11.0		1.46	100					1.80
Italy	51.1	4.2	6.9	15.7	22.1	1.75	53.3	36.1	10.3	0.2		3.60
Latvia	50.7	2.3	4.1	20.4	22.5	1.47	75.8	24.2				2.55
Liechtenstein	37.8	5.4	45.9	2.7	8.1	1.58	91.9	8.1				2.09
Lithuania	48.8	4.2	11.3	24.9	10.7	1.43	87.3	12.7				2.80
Luxembourg	3.1			2.4	94.5	5.14	5.5	6.8	42.5	45.2		8.03
Malta							100					0.00
Monaco												
Montenegro	58.4	9.4	17.8	14.4		1.15	100					0.66
Netherlands	6.4	0.4	1.2	3.6	88.4	3.95	11.7	10.9	76.3	1.1		6.93
North Macedonia	42.9	15.2	31.6	10.3		1.36	100.0					1.38
Norway	83.8	7.5	6.3	2.5		0.63	100.0					0.58
Poland	24.7	4.4	14.7	41.1	15.0	2.00	69.7	30.0	0.3			3.04
Portugal	35.1	3.6	13.4	30.7	17.1	1.81	77.4	16.6	5.2	0.8		2.23
Romania	14.5	10.7	35.3	39.2	0.4	1.82	97.7	2.3				2.28
San Marino		21.6	73.0	5.4		1.65	100.0					2.92
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	9.8	3.7	14.9	57.1	14.6	1.94	83.1	16.9				2.44
Slovakia	5.3	3.2	14.8	40.8	35.8	2.70	63.9	32.4	3.7			3.13
Slovenia	1.6		0.6	5.5	92.3	3.85	16.7	72.0	11.3			4.76
Spain	68.1	2.7	6.5	16.1	6.6	0.92	93.3	5.9	0.8			1.22
Sweden	90.2	3.1	3.4	1.4	2.0	0.29	98.3	1.5	0.2			0.47
Switzerland	11.2	1.9	5.2	9.6	72.1	3.84	32.2	29.5	38.3	0.0		4.51
Türkiye	93.2	2.7	3.2	0.9	0.0	0.52	99.6	0.4				0.86
Total	42.9	3.2	8.8	16.1	29.0	1.98	65.8	16.6	15.0	2.6		3.12
Total without Türkiye	33.8	3.3	9.8	18.9	34.3	2.25	59.7	19.5	17.7	3.1		3.53
EEA-38	42.9	3.2	8.8	16.1	29.0	1.98	65.8	16.6	15.0	2.6		3.12
EEA-38 without Türkiye	33.8	3.3	9.8	18.9	34.3	2.25	59.7	19.5	17.7	3.1		3.53
EEA-32	43.4	3.0	8.3	15.3	30.0	2.02	64.6	17.0	15.7	2.8		3.18
EEA-32 without Türkiye	33.8	3.0	9.3	18.1	35.8	2.31	57.9	20.1	18.6	3.3		3.62
EU-27	33.9	3.0	9.3	18.2	35.6	2.30	58.1	20.1	18.5	3.3		3.62
Northern Europe	71.5	3.0	5.8	9.8	9.8	0.99	91.1	8.8	0.1			1.57
Western Europe	3.6	0.7	5.2	3.8	86.8	4.05	12.0	13.8	55.3	18.9		7.06
Central Europe	12.0	2.1	6.8	21.8	57.3	3.23	34.0	34.0	30.7	1.3		4.74
Southern Europe	57.7	3.2	7.1	18.5	13.6	1.34	75.5	20.3	4.1	0.1		2.27
South-Eastern Europe	60.4	5.2	14.6	17.4	2.5	1.12	96.1	3.8	0.1			1.47
Kosovo	19.0	7.0	25.9	47.5	0.7	2.32	100					1.58
Serbia (without Kosovo)	8.5	3.3	13.4	58.3	16.5	1.89	80.8	19.2				2.55

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed agricultural area exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05%. Empty cells mean no agricultural area in exposure.

Figures 3.3 and 3.4 show the frequency distribution of the wheat and potato agricultural area over some O₃ exposure classes (in terms of POD₆ for wheat and potato) for each country, for five large European regions, for EU-27, for EEA-32 (with and without Türkiye) and for the total mapping area, for years 2022 and 2023. The figures present graphically the core information of Tables 3.3 and 3.4.

Figure 3.3 Percentage of the wheat and potato agricultural area (%) exposed to different values of the indicator POD₆ for wheat (above) and POD₆ for potato (below) (mmol/m² PLA), 2022

Figure 3.4 Percentage of the wheat and potato agricultural area (%) exposed to different values of the indicator POD_6 for wheat (above) and POD_6 for potato (below) ($mmol/m^2$ PLA), 2023

4 Comparison of the new indicator based on POD_{γ} and the current AIR004 indicator based on AOT40 results

In this chapter, the results of the new indicator based on POD_{γ} are compared with the current AIR004 indicator based on the AOT40 metric. In addition, the basic and alternative variants of the new POD_{γ} -based indicator are mutually compared, and also the wheat and potato parts of the alternative POD_{γ} -based indicator.

Figure 4.1 presents the scatter plots showing the correlation between the agricultural area weighted values of (i) POD_{γ} in different variants and (ii) AOT40 for vegetation, as calculated for individual countries, both for 2022 and 2023.

Figure 4.1 Correlation between agricultural area weighted values of POD_{3IAM} for crops (left), POD_6 for wheat (middle) and POD_6 for potato (right) (y-axis) versus agricultural area weighted values of AOT40 for vegetation (x-axis) per country for years 2022 (above) and 2023 (below)

Looking at the results, one can see quite a poor correlation between the weighted values of POD_{γ} (for all variants) and AOT40 for vegetation.

Figure 4.2 presents the scatter plots showing the correlation between the agricultural area weighted values of (i) POD_6 for wheat or potato and (ii) POD_{3IAM} for crops, and also between (i) POD_6 for potato and (ii) POD_6 for wheat, as calculated for individual countries. The correlation shows the level of relationship between two parameters, i.e. the level of interchangeability of these parameters.

The results show stronger correlation between the weighted values of the three different variants of POD_{γ} , compared to the correlation between the weighted values of POD_{γ} and AOT40 (as shown in Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.2 Correlation between agricultural area weighted values of POD₆ for wheat (left) and POD₆ for potato (middle and right) (y-axis) versus agricultural area weighted values of POD₃IAM for crops (left and middle) and POD₆ for wheat (right) (x-axis) per country for years 2022 (above) and 2023 (below)

Map 4.1 presents inter-annual differences for AOT40 for vegetation (as used for the current AIR004 indicator) and for the three different variants of POD_γ (as applied for the new POD_γ-based indicator, either in the basic or the alternative variants).

One can see that the inter-annual differences of AOT40 for vegetation show different patterns compared to the inter-annual differences of the three POD_γ variants. On the other hand, the inter-annual difference of the three POD_γ variants shows quite similar patterns (despite some differences).

Huge differences in both spatial distribution and inter-annual variability between AOT40 and POD_γ metrics are in agreement with the well-known facts, already mentioned before, that high ambient O₃ concentrations do not lead to high O₃ fluxes when stomata are closed during unfavourable environmental conditions and that, conversely, quite low O₃ concentrations can still lead to fairly high O₃ fluxes when stomata are open under favourable environmental conditions. Another reason for the different spatial and temporal distributions of AOT40 and POD_γ might be that the AOT40 gives more weight to peak ozone concentrations due to the cut-off at 80 µg/m³ (i.e. 40 ppb), while the POD_γ indicators are more sensitive to variations of background O₃ levels.

Map 4.1 Difference in concentrations between 2022 and 2023 for ozone indicators AOT40 for vegetation (upper left), POD_{3IAM} for crops (upper right), POD_6 for wheat (bottom left) and POD_6 for potato (bottom right)

Based on the results of both the correlation scatterplots and the inter-annual difference maps, it is concluded that the new AIR indicator based on POD_{γ} should complement the current AIR004 indicator, not substitute it, in order to ensure a more comprehensive risk analysis based on current knowledge. Apart from that, as all variants of POD_{γ} show similarities, it is concluded that the new indicator based on the POD_{3IAM} for crops can be fairly used to represent different crop species at regional to continental scales, which is relevant for the European-wide POD_{γ} -based indicator, with species-specific POD_{γ} estimates more suitable for more specific risk assessments, in agreement with the CLRTAP methodology.

Adopting a dual approach based on AOT40 (exposure) and POD_{γ} (dose) is therefore not a duplication but a logical step to improve the assessment of the O_3 burden and the associated risk of negative effects on vegetation. While the environmental exposure expressed by AOT40 allows relatively simple monitoring of air quality and long-term exposure trends, the absorbed dose expressed by POD_{γ} is a metric with biological relevance capable of explaining damage to crops and ecosystems. Particularly, the use of both metrics should be recommended for areas where asynchrony between plant physiological activity and high O_3 concentrations due to weather conditions or climate change is suspected. Keeping both complementary metrics would ensure a better estimation of risks.

5 Discussion of the reasons for POD_Y levels and inter-annual variability

POD_Y is a multifactorial indicator influenced by both atmospheric O_3 concentration and physiological activity of the target vegetation. It is the accumulated stomatal O_3 flux (F_{sto}) above a threshold of Y during a specified time or growth period (for its calculation, see Annex 1, Eq. A1.5). The hourly stomatal O_3 flux is calculated using the O_3 concentration at the top of the canopy, the stomatal conductance (g_{sto}) and the quasi-laminar and the leaf surface resistances (see Annex 1, Eq. A1.3). The O_3 concentration at the canopy top is calculated using the ambient O_3 concentration and different resistances (see Annex 1, Eq. A1.1), while the stomatal conductance is calculated using the species-specific maximum stomatal conductance and six limitation functions (see Annex 1, Eq. A1.2). As a result, the POD_Y levels and their inter-annual variability are difficult to interpret without disentangling the respective contributions of each limiting function to the actual absorbed O_3 flux. This chapter presents an analysis of the contributions of each limitation function to the POD_Y and their inter-annual variation between 2022 and 2023. The analysis has been performed for POD_6 for wheat for 2022 and 2023 (see Map 3.3 left and Map 3.4 left). The main reason for selecting this POD_Y variant was that the maps of the POD_6 for wheat has been created under the ETC HE since 2018, so that the ETC HE has more experience with this indicator, compared to the POD_3IAM for crops. This chapter plays a role as a case study, as it aims to analyse the inter-annual POD_Y differences (which was not done so far under the ETC HE). Apart from that, due to the similarities between POD_6 for wheat and POD_3IAM for crops (see Chapter 4), some of its results might be applicable to POD_3IAM for crops as well.

To evaluate the physiological limitations affecting O_3 uptake in European wheat crops, a relative indicator was constructed based on a data-driven modelling framework. This indicator allows to quantify how much each physiological function reduces the potential O_3 flux, offering a meaningful and interpretable perspective on the stomatal limitation landscape across biogeographical regions or countries. Based on this, the main parameters that influence the POD_Y levels can be seen, next to the O_3 concentrations.

The input data for calculating this indicator consist of hourly values for the following physiological limitation functions for wheat that have been used in the computation of the POD_6 for wheat:

- f_{phen} (phenology),
- f_{O_3} (O_3 response),
- f_{light} (light),
- f_{temp} (temperature),
- f_{VPD} (vapour pressure deficit),
- f_{SMI} (soil moisture index)

These values have been spatially aggregated over biogeographical regions or countries for a full growing season (e.g. a unique value of each function for each region/country at each hour of the growing period for the years 2022 and 2023 is obtained by averaging values of all grid cells of the relevant region or country) making it possible to recompute an aggregated POD_Y that is called POD_Y of reference (POD_{Y_ref}). However, the spatial aggregation has an effect on the recalculation of this POD_{Y_ref} . Indeed, the recomputed F_{sto} does not exceed the 6 nmol/m² PLA per second threshold as often as when calculated at 2 km resolution. The reason is that the limitation functions as well as the O_3 concentration are smoothed by the spatial aggregation. As a consequence, the accumulation of POD_{6_ref} account for just a few hours (when F_{sto} exceed 6 nmol/m² PLA per second) in the whole year, which is not enough to be used for an analysis of the contribution of the limitation functions. Therefore, the threshold of 3 nmol/m² PLA per second for F_{sto} is preferred to the classical threshold of 6 nmol/m² PLA per second allowing a larger temporal cover to be used for this sensitivity analysis. So, the POD_{Y_ref} indicator is called POD_{3_ref} in order to take into account this threshold value.

5.1 Methodology: Definition of the relative Indicator

For each limitation function f , the following values have been computed:

- The reference cumulative O_3 flux (POD_3_ref) using all the limiting functions aggregated over biogeographical regions or countries. (For biogeographical regions, see Annex 1, Map A1.1.)
- A modified O_3 flux ($POD_3_without_f$) by **setting function f to 1 wherever its original value was non-zero**, keeping other functions unchanged. (meaning that function f has no effect on the total flux $POD_3_without_f$)

The indicator “Contribution $_f$ ” is then defined as:

$$\text{Contribution}_f = \frac{POD_3_without_f - POD_3_ref}{POD_3_without_f} * 100 \quad (5.1)$$

This represents the percentage of the O_3 flux lost specifically due to function f , relative to the potential flux without its limitation. Therefore, it is an indicator of the effectiveness of the limitation: "how much of the potential $POD_3_without_f$ has been limited by this function?"

The advantage of the indicator is that it offers an independent measure for each function, without interference from others. It can be used on either bioregion-aggregated data or country-level data without changing methodology. It will allow the identification of the dominant limiting functions in each region or country but also the assessment of how physiological stresses differ between years (e.g. 2022 vs 2023). However, considering that the effectiveness of the limitation is related to each $POD_3_without_f$, the sum of the effectiveness of the limitation for all function is not 100%.

To validate the approach, it is necessary to check that the POD_3_ref calculated from aggregated data over biogeographical regions or countries is well correlated with the original POD_6 for wheat values which were computed at grid cell level and then aggregated to the biogeographical regions / countries. The analysis of the different POD calculation shows a correlation which is quite high for the inter-annual differences, ($R^2 = 0.74$ for countries, $R^2 = 0.89$ for biogeographical regions), see Figure 5.1. Thus, the results of the analysis for the recomputed POD_3 can be applied for explaining the inter-annual differences of the original POD_6 for wheat.

Figure 5.1 Correlation between POD_3_ref for wheat calculated based on spatially aggregated limiting functions (y-axis) versus spatial average of POD_6 for wheat (calculated at 2 km resolution) (x-axis) for aggregations over countries (left) and biogeographical regions (right), inter-annual difference 2023-2022

5.2 Results

The results from this analysis are presented with:

- Inter-annual differences in POD_3_ref (2023-2022) at country level (Figure 5.2) and biogeographical region level (Annex 3, Figure A3.1 left).
- Inter-annual differences in the efficiency of the reduction of POD_3_ref for f_{phen} , f_{temp} , f_{SMI} , f_{VPD} (2023-2022) at country level (Figure 5.3, Figure 5.4, Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6, since those functions are the most limiting ones of the six considered functions) and biogeographical region level (Annex 3, Figure A3.1 right).
- Heatmaps of POD_3_ref and heatmaps of the different contributions of the functions for years 2022 and 2023 (Figure 5.7 and Figure 5.8 for aggregation at the country level and Annex 3, Figure A3.2 and Figure A3.3 for aggregation at the level of biogeographical regions).

Figure 5.2 POD_3_ref for wheat inter-annual variation: 2023-2022, country level, in mmol/m² PLA

Figure 5.7 POD₃_ref for wheat in mmol/m² PLA (left) and efficiency of the limitation functions for its reduction in % (right) in 2022 for countries

Figure 5.8 POD₃_ref for wheat in mmol/m² PLA (left) and efficiency of the limitation functions for its reduction in % (right) and in 2023 for countries

Looking at the POD_3_{ref} development between 2022 and 2023 for aggregation at country level (Figure 5.2), it shows that the Northern countries (Finland, Baltic countries), some countries around Mediterranean (Spain, Albania, Cyprus, Italy, Greece, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo), Bulgaria and some Alpine countries (Austria, Switzerland) have an aggregated POD_3_{ref} higher in 2022 than 2023. For other countries, mostly in the western and central Europe (Luxembourg, Belgium, Slovakia, Ireland, Germany, Netherlands, Hungary, France, Poland, Czechia, Slovenia, Portugal), a POD_3_{ref} increase from 2022 to 2023 is seen. Focusing at biogeographical regions level (Annex 3, Figure A3.1), one can see the highest POD_3_{ref} increases for Continental, Atlantic, Pannonian and Steppic biogeographical regions, while the steepest decrease for the Mediterranean biogeographical region.

Regarding the POD_3_{ref} results at country level for the efficiency of reduction (Figure 5.7 and Figure 5.8), f_{phen} , f_{temp} and to a lesser extent f_{SMI} seems to be the major restrictive functions for POD_3_{ref} in a lot of countries for both year 2022 and 2023. f_{VPD} is never the highest restrictive function.

Regarding the biogeographical regions (Annex 3, Figures A3.2 and A3.3): For 2022, the main efficiency reduction is for f_{phen} for all regions except Atlantic and Arctic regions (for which the highest is f_{temp}), which is mostly followed by f_{temp} . f_{SMI} remains high in Anatolian, Boreal and Alpine regions. For 2023, the main efficiency reduction come also from f_{phen} for all regions except Atlantic and Arctic regions (f_{temp}), followed mostly by f_{temp} . f_{SMI} remains high in Boreal, Anatolian and Mediterranean regions.

In the end, one can say:

- two limitation functions play a **major role**: f_{phen} and f_{temp}
- f_{SMI} is a bit less restrictive followed by f_{VPD} very often less restrictive
- f_{O_3} is almost never restrictive because it always has greater value than f_{phen}
- **behaviour** of limitation functions are not the same between countries (or biogeographical regions)
- **inter-annual variation of the POD_3** is due to the combination of the restrictiveness of f_{phen} , f_{temp} , f_{SMI} and f_{VPD} and depends also on the level of the O_3 concentration. The analysis shows that there is no general pattern in the behaviour of the limitation functions that may explain this inter-annual variation between 2022 and 2023.
- These results reflect the inter-annual variability in O_3 concentration and growing conditions, showing that a two year long period is not long enough to extract meaningful conclusions about trends in O_3 effect risks. However, this exercise is useful to understand the level of temporal and geographical variability of the POD_y .

6 Conclusions and recommendations

This report proposes a new indicator based on POD_V as complementary information to the current EEA indicator *AIR004 – Exposure of Europe’s ecosystem to ozone*, which consists of two parts related to the agricultural and forested areas. Similarly to the AIR004, the new POD_V -based indicator should also show the O_3 exposure of crops and forests separately. This report develops the first part of the new indicator, which is related to the flux-related O_3 exposure of crops. The flux-related O_3 exposure of forest trees is suggested to be developed in 2026.

Two options of the new indicator related to the crops are considered, i.e. the crop specific POD_V indicator and a more generic metric based on the POD_V used in the Integrated Assessment Modelling (i.e. POD_VIAM), which can be applied for different crops. The advantage of the crop specific POD_V metric is in its more exact estimation of the O_3 impacts on the corresponding crop, however, it should be applied only to areas covered by this specific crop. On the other hand, the POD_VIAM is more suitable for estimating the O_3 impacts on the wide variety of crops, and thus it can be applied to areas covered by crops in general. For this reason, the metric POD_3IAM for crops is recommended to be used in the POD_V -based indicator for crops.

In the report, the POD_3IAM for crops has been applied as a basic option for this new indicator. Its results for 2022 and 2023 have been calculated and analysed. Additionally, as an alternative option, also the crop specific metrics POD_6 for wheat and potato have been applied. Subsequently, the results of the new indicator based on the POD_3IAM for crops metrics have been compared with the current AIR004 indicator based on the AOT40 for vegetation metric. In addition, the basic and alternative options of the new POD_V -based indicator have also been mutually compared. Based on the results of both the correlation scatterplots and the inter-annual difference maps, it has been concluded that the new AIR indicator based on POD_V should complement the current AIR004 indicator rather than substitute it, in order to ensure a more comprehensive risk analysis based on current knowledge. Apart from that, it has been concluded that the new indicator based on the POD_3IAM for crops can be fairly used to represent different crop species.

In the report, the POD_3IAM for crops indicator have been applied for the same agricultural areas as for which is applied the current AIR004 indicator (i.e. for CLC level-1 class No. 2 “Agricultural areas”). However, its applicability also for pastures that are included in these agricultural areas (i.e. for CLC level-2 class No. 2.3) should be examined in the future, i.e. whether the use of risk indicators specific for pastures does not lead into a considerable change in areas under the risk of O_3 negative effects.

The results support the view that AOT40 and POD_V should be considered as complementary indicators (or environmental policy tools). While the AOT40 is more relevant for exposure analysis and air quality trends, the POD_V represents a more effects-oriented indicator for vegetation because it reflects the O_3 dose actually absorbed by plants. The combination of both approaches provides a more comprehensive picture of the exposure to O_3 and the associated risk of effects on European vegetation.

Adopting a dual approach based on AOT40 (exposure) and POD_V (dose) is therefore not a duplication but a logical step to improve the assessment of the O_3 burden and the associated risk of negative effects on vegetation. While the environmental exposure expressed by AOT40 allows relatively simple monitoring of air quality and long-term exposure trends, the absorbed dose expressed by POD_V is a metric with biological relevance capable of explaining damage to crops and ecosystems. It is therefore recommended that both AOT40- and POD_V -based indicators continue to be analysed and reported in the long term, in order to enable to identify trends in the risk of negative effects.

At the same time, the AOT40 is currently the only O_3 indicator included in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU, 2024) for the protection of vegetation and next to this, its levels can be simply calculated

based on the O₃ monitoring data. Therefore, it should further continue to be applied. Its complementary use with more biologically meaningful and effects-oriented indicators for vegetation protection like POD_γ should be promoted. However, at the same time, one should bear in mind that in contrast to the AOT40, the POD_γ calculation is quite complex and the POD_γ values are highly sensitive to the setting of different parameters used in their calculation.

POD_γ is a complex indicator, which depends on different variables. High ambient O₃ concentrations do not necessarily lead to high POD_γ values, e.g., if stomata are closed during unfavourable environmental conditions. Conversely, quite low O₃ concentrations can still lead to fairly high O₃ fluxes (and POD_γ values) when stomata are open under favourable environmental conditions. For that reason, the POD_γ levels and inter-annual differences are in general difficult to be understood. Thus, in addition to the development and testing of the new POD_γ-based air indicator, the reasons for the POD_γ levels and inter-annual differences have been analysed and discussed in the report for POD_γ for wheat, as a case study. It seems that phenology and temperature and also soil moisture in water-limited regions play a major role in the POD_γ levels, apart from the O₃ concentrations.

As a follow-up of this report, it is recommended for the next period to develop also the second part of the POD_γ-based indicator, i.e. the one related to forest trees.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
AOT40	Accumulated Ozone exposure over a Threshold of 40 ppb (i.e. 80 µg/m ³) in a specific period	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024L2881
AQ	Air quality	
CLC	Corine Land Cover	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover
CLRTAP	Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (Air Convention)	https://unece.org/environment-policy/air
EEA	European Environment Agency	www.eea.europa.eu
EEA-32	the 32 EEA member countries (EU-27 + Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland and Turkey)	https://www.eea.europa.eu/help/glossary/eea-glossary/eea-32
EEA-38	the 38 EEA member and cooperating countries (EEA-32 plus Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo under UN Security Council Resolution 1244/99, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia)	https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/about/working-practices/docs-register/eea-writing-manual
EMEP	The co-operative programme for monitoring and evaluation of the long-range transmission of air pollutants in Europe	https://www.emep.int
EIONET	European Environment Information and Observation Network	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/
ETC HE	European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs
EU-27	the 27 EU Member States (as of 1 February 2020)	https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/about/working-practices/docs-register/eea-writing-manual
IAM	Integrated Assessment Modelling	
ICP Vegetation	International Cooperative Programme on Effects of Air Pollution on Natural Vegetation and Crops	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/
NILU	Norwegian Institute for Air Research	https://www.nilu.no/
PLA	Projected Leaf Area	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
POD _Y	Phytotoxic Ozone Dose above a threshold of Y nmol/m ² PLA per second	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
POD _Y IAM	POD _Y for a vegetation type for application in large-scale modelling such as integrated assessment modelling (POD _Y IAM), accumulated over a stated time period during daylight hours.	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
POD _Y SPEC	POD _Y for a specific plant species or group of plant species (POD _Y SPEC), accumulated over a stated time period during daylight hours.	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
VOCs	volatile organic compounds	

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Annex 1 Methodology

A1.1 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose above a threshold flux Y (POD_Y) calculation

The calculation of the phytotoxic O₃ dose, as outlined below, follows the methodology described in the Manual for modelling and mapping critical loads & levels of the Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution Convention (CLRTAP) in its most recent available revision (CLRTAP, 2024), including some specifications presented in the Scientific background documents of this manual (CLRTAP, 2017, 2020), as prepared by the International scientific Cooperative Programme on effects of air pollution on natural vegetation and crops of the Working Group on Effects of the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation). The steps to be taken are presented in Table A1.1.

Table A1.1 Steps to be taken to calculate exceedance of flux-based (POD_YSPEC or POD_YIAM) critical levels

1	Decide on the species and biogeographical region(s) to be included.
2	Obtain the O ₃ concentrations at the top of the canopy for the species or vegetation-specific accumulation period.
3	Calculate the hourly stomatal conductance of O ₃ (g _{sto}).
4	Model the hourly stomatal flux of O ₃ (F _{sto}).
5	Calculation of POD _Y (POD _Y SPEC or POD _Y IAM) from F _{sto} .

Source: CLRTAP, 2024.

The cumulative stomatal O₃ fluxes (F_{sto}) are calculated over the course of the growing season based on ambient O₃ concentration and stomatal conductance (g_{sto}) to O₃. g_{sto} is calculated using a multiplicative stomatal conductance model proposed by Jarvis (1976) and modified by Emberson et al. (2000a) as a function of species-specific maximum g_{sto} (expressed on a projected leaf-area basis), phenology, and prevailing environmental conditions (photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD)), air temperature, vapour pressure deficit (VPD), and soil moisture.

Hourly averaged stomatal O₃ fluxes (F_{sto}) in excess of a threshold Y (expressed in mmol/m² PLA⁽¹⁾) are accumulated over a species or vegetation-specific accumulation period during daylight hours, in order to get the phytotoxic O₃ dose above the threshold Y (POD_Y).

Two POD_Y versions are available in CLRTAP (2017a): POD_YIAM (which is a simplified version recommended for Integrated Assessment Modelling) and POD_YSPEC (which is specific to a given specie). Here, the calculation of POD_YSPEC for wheat and potato (labelled further simply as POD₆ for wheat and potato) is presented. Simplifications and differences in the calculation of POD₃IAM for crops compared to POD₆SPEC for wheat and potato are provided in Box 2.

⁽¹⁾ PLA, or the projected leaf area, is the total area of the sides of the leaves that are projected towards the sun. PLA is different to the total leaf area, which accounts for both sides of the leaves.

Box 2 Simplifications and differences in the calculation of POD_YIAM compared to POD_YSPEC

A flux-threshold Y

Due to difficulties in estimating the O₃ flux using Y = 6 nmol/m² PLA per second in large scale modelling and IAM arising from the strong increase in the uncertainty in modelled POD with increasing Y, Y = 3 nmol/m² PLA per second is to be used (POD₃IAM).

f_{phen} and f_{O3}

The simplified flux models suitable for POD_YIAM do not include the modifying effect of phenology and O₃ in the case of crops on the stomatal conductance, hence f_{phen} and f_{O3} for crops are set to 1 between the start and the end of the accumulation period.

f_{sw}

The simplified flux models suitable for IAM do not include the modifying effect of soil moisture on the stomatal conductance, hence f_{sw} is set to 1 between the start and the end of the accumulation period. Using the simplified flux models as a stand-alone application, this method would indicate the risk of O₃ damage under the worst case scenario where soil moisture is not limiting stomatal O₃ flux. However, the effect of soil moisture is important and in large-scale applications, surrogate indices are usually applied such as the Soil Moisture Index in the EMEP model (Simpson et al., 2012). Thus, f_{SMI} (where SMI represents the Soil Moisture Index) as routinely used in the calculations of POD₆SPEC for wheat and potato is used in this report also for the calculation of POD₃IAM for crops.

A_{start_ETS} and A_{end_ETS}

To accommodate the need for IAM to use a longer time period than the thermal time-based time window used for POD₆SPEC, POD₃IAM is accumulated over 90 days, centred on the timing of mid-anthesis (flowering) in wheat. Therefore, A_{start_ETS} and A_{end_ETS} are set to be 45 days before mid-anthesis in wheat and 45 days after mid-anthesis in wheat, respectively.

Source: CLRTAP, 2024

Obtaining the ozone concentrations at the top of the canopy for the species or vegetation-specific accumulation period

The O₃ concentration at the top of the canopy (nmol/m³) in the given hour H is calculated according to

$$c(z_1) = c(z_{m, O_3}) * \left[1 - \frac{R_a(z_{tgt}, z_{m, O_3})}{R_a(d+z_0, z_{m, O_3}) + R_b + R_{surf}} \right] \quad (A1.1)$$

where $c(z_1)$ is O₃ concentration at the top of the canopy,
 $c(z_{m, O_3})$ is the O₃ concentration estimated based on measurements at the height z_m, (see Eq. A1.6),
 $R_a(x, y)$ is the aerodynamic resistance between the height of y and the height of x,
 R_b is the resistance to O₃ diffusion in the laminar sub-layer,
 R_{surf} is the overall resistance to O₃ deposition to the underlying surfaces,

$$\text{while } R_a(z_{tgt}, z_{m, O_3}) = \frac{1}{k \cdot u^*} \left[\ln \left(\frac{z_{m, O_3} - d}{z_{tgt} - d} \right) - \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_{m, O_3} - d}{L} \right) + \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_{tgt} - d}{L} \right) \right] \quad (A1.1a)$$

$$R_a(d + z_0, z_{m, O_3}) = \frac{1}{k \cdot u^*} \left[\ln \left(\frac{z_{m, O_3} - d}{z_0} \right) - \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_{m, O_3} - d}{L} \right) + \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_0}{L} \right) \right] \quad (A1.1b)$$

$$R_b = \frac{2}{k \cdot u^*} \left(\frac{Sc}{Pr} \right)^{2/3} \quad (A1.1c)$$

$$R_{surf} = \frac{1}{\frac{LAI}{R_{sto}} + \frac{SAI}{R_{ext}} + \frac{1}{R_{inc} + R_{soil}}} \quad (A1.1d)$$

where k is the von Kármán constant (equal to 0.41),
 z_{tgt} is the top canopy height (the target height),
 z_{m, O_3} is the height of the available O₃ measurement above the canopy,

z_0 is the roughness length, usually assumed as 1/10 of the canopy height,
 L is the Obukhov length,
 d is the displacement height, usually assumed as 2/3 of the canopy height,
 u^* is the friction velocity,
 Sc is the Schmidt number for O_3 (equal to 0.41),
 Pr is the Prandtl number of air (equal to 0.71),
 LAI is the projected leaf area in (m^2/m^2),
 SAI is the surface area of the canopy in (m^2/m^2),
 $\Psi_H(\dots) = \Psi_H(\zeta)$ is the similarity function for heat with ζ as the argument ⁽²⁾,

according to

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\zeta) &= 2 && \text{when } \zeta < 0 \\
 &= -5\zeta && \text{when } \zeta \geq 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{A1.1e}$$

with $x = (1 - 16 * \zeta)^{1/4}$ (A1.1f)

and R_{ext} is the resistance to cuticular deposition of O_3 (equal to 2,500 s/m);

R_{soil} is the soil resistance (equal to 200 s/m¹),

while $R_{sto} = 1/g_{sto}$ (A1.1g)

$R_{inc} = b.SAI.h/u^*$ (A1.1h)

where g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance,

b is the empirical constant (equal to 14 m⁻¹),

h is the height of the canopy.

The calculations of LAI and SAI are based on Simpson et al. (2012) and Emberson et al. (2000b), as well as the schematics regarding LAI presented therein (see Eq. 2.8i to 2.8n).

$$LAI = LAI_{min} + (d - SGS) * (LAI_{max} - LAI_{min}) / SGS_{length}, \tag{A1.1i}$$

$$SAI = 5 * LAI / 3.5 \tag{A1.1j}$$

when $SGS \leq d < SGS + SGS_{length}$

$$LAI = LAI_{max}, \tag{A1.1k}$$

$$SAI = LAI + 1.5, \tag{A1.1l}$$

when $SGS + SGS_{length} \leq d < EGS - EGS_{length}$

$$LAI = LAI_{max} - (d - (EGS - EGS_{length})) * (LAI_{max} - LAI_{min}) / EGS_{length}, \tag{A1.1m}$$

$$SAI = LAI + 1.5, \tag{A1.1n}$$

when $EGS - EGS_{length} \leq d < EGS$

where LAI_{min} is the minimum (within the growing season) LAI values (m^2/m^2)

LAI_{max} is the maximum (within the growing season) LAI values (m^2/m^2)

SGS is the start of the growing season (day of year)

SGS_{length} is the duration of the start of the growing season (days)

EGS_{length} is the duration of the end of the growing season (days)

EGS is the end of the growing season (day of year)

Calculation of the hourly stomatal conductance of ozone (g_{sto})

The basis of the approach used for calculating phytotoxic O_3 doses is the calculation of an instantaneous stomatal conductance g_{sto} in the given hour H, according to the equation

⁽²⁾ For more details see CLRTAP (2017).

$$g_{sto} = g_{max} * [\min(f_{phen}, f_{O3})] * f_{light} * \max[f_{min}, (f_{temp} * f_{VPD} * f_{SW})] \quad (A1.2)$$

where g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance in (mmol O₃ /m² PLA per second),
 g_{max} is the species-specific maximum stomatal conductance in (mmol O₃ /m² PLA per second), see Table A1.3,
 f_{phen} is the relative proportion function for the phenology for the different stage of growing; for POD_vIAM, f_{phen} is set to 1 (see Box 2),
 f_{O3} is the relative proportion function for the influence of O₃ on stomatal flux by promoting premature senescence; for POD_vIAM, f_{phen} is set to 1 (see Box 2),
 f_{min} is the species-specific relative minimum stomatal conductance that occurs during daylight hours, see Tables A1.3 and A1.4,
 $f_{temp}, f_{VPD}, f_{SW}, f_{light}$ are relative proportion functions for leaf stomata respond to temperature, air humidity, soil moisture and light.

Parameters $f_{phen}, f_{O3}, f_{light}, f_{temp}, f_{VPD}, f_{SW}$ and f_{min} are expressed as relative proportion functions, taking values between 0 and 1 as a proportion of g_{max} . These functions allow taking into account irradiance (f_{light}), temperature (f_{temp}), water vapour deficit at leaves level (f_{VPD}), soil moisture (f_{sw}), phenology for the different stage of growing (f_{phen}) and the influence of O₃ on stomatal flux by promoting premature senescence (f_{O3}). f_{min} is the minimum relative value of stomatal conductance during the daylight.

The parameter f_{phen} is calculated based on the accumulation of thermal time over the growing season of the crop being considered (Colette et al., 2018), according to CLRTAP (2024)). For wheat and potato, the accumulation period is defined for each year using the effective temperature sum (ETS) in °C for days in excess of 0 °C.

For wheat, the total accumulation period during which wheat is sensitive to O₃ exposure is 200 °C days and 300 °C days before mid-anthesis (mid-point in flowering) to 700 °C days to 550 °C days after mid-anthesis for Atlantic, Boreal and Continental regions and Mediterranean region, respectively. The timing of mid-anthesis is estimated by starting at the first date after 1 January (or just 1 January) when the temperature exceeds 0 °C. The mean daily temperature is then accumulated (temperature sum), and mid-anthesis is estimated to be a temperature sum of 1,075 °C days for Atlantic, Boreal and Continental regions and 1,250 °C days for Mediterranean region, which in general corresponds to bread wheat.

For potato, the accumulation period stands between 330 °C days before the tuber initiation date and 800 °C days after this date. The tuber initiation date is considered to be homogeneous throughout Europe. The reasons for its simplification are a) heterogeneous climatic conditions in the European countries naturally lead to different time of potato planting (Pedersen et al., 2005) followed by different time of the tuber initiation and b) lack of detailed local data availability for. As discussed ⁽³⁾ with the French national Chamber of agriculture (APCA, <http://chambres-agriculture.fr>), the tuber initiation starts 15 days after the transplantation in the field, which occurs in May. Therefore, the fixed date for the tuber initiation was set to June 1st.

The accumulation period for POD₃IAM is defined as a 90-day time window centred on the timing of mid-anthesis (flowering) in wheat. Consequently, the start of the accumulation period (A_{start}) is set to

⁽³⁾ There is a lack of information on a date of potato tuber initiation in Europe. It should ideally rely on existing models based on agricultural practices, local climatology, ground properties, and location. INERIS, while developing the POD script, relied on contents of discussions with the French National Chamber of Agriculture (consultation with APCA, March 2018; Deumier and Hannon, 2010). Based on the information given that the tuber initiation starts 15 days after the transplantation in the field, which occurs in May in France, a fixed date of June 1st has been chosen for France and applied also for the rest of Europe. This date should be revised according to the availability of more accurate information on potato plantations in Europe.

45 days before mid-anthesis, and the end of the accumulation period (A_{end}) is set to 45 days after mid-anthesis; see Table A1.4.

The parameter f_{phen} is calculated according to following equations:

in the case of wheat:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{phen} &= 1 && \text{when } (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_1_ETS}) \leq ETS \leq (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_3_ETS}) \\
 f_{phen} &= 1 - \left(\frac{f_{phen_a}}{f_{phen_4_ETS} - f_{phen_3_ETS}} \right) * (ETS - f_{phen_3_ETS}) \\
 &&& \text{when } (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_3_ETS}) < ETS \leq (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_4_ETS}) \\
 f_{phen} &= f_{phen_e} - \left(\frac{f_{phen_e}}{f_{phen_5_ETS} - f_{phen_4_ETS}} \right) * (ETS - f_{phen_4_ETS}) \\
 &&& \text{when } (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_4_ETS}) < ETS \leq f_{phen_5_ETS} \quad (A1.2a)
 \end{aligned}$$

in the case of potato (formulated based on CLRTAP, 2017):

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{phen} &= 1 - \left(\frac{1 - f_{phen_a}}{f_{phen_1_ETS}} \right) * ETS && \text{when } f_{phen_1_ETS} \leq ETS < 0 \\
 f_{phen} &= 1 - \left(\frac{1 - f_{phen_e}}{f_{phen_2_ETS}} \right) * ETS && \text{when } 0 < ETS \leq f_{phen_2_ETS} \quad (A1.2b)
 \end{aligned}$$

in the case of POD₃IAM:

$$f_{phen} = 1 \quad (A1.2c)$$

where ETS is the effective temperature sum in °C days using a base temperature of 0 °C for wheat and potato (see Table A1.3);
for wheat, ETS is set to 0 °C days at mid-anthesis day. Then A_{start_ETS} will be at 200 °C days before mid-anthesis, and A_{end_ETS} will be at 700 °C days after mid-anthesis over a base temperature of 0 °C;
for potato, ETS is set to 0 °C days at tuber initiation day. Then A_{start_ETS} will be at 330 °C days before tuber initiation and A_{end_ETS} at 800 °C days after tuber initiation over a base temperature of 0 °C;
 f_{phen_a}, f_{phen_e} is the phenology function, which consists of terms describing rate changes of g_{max} expressed as fractions (see Table A1.3),
 $f_{phen_1_ETS}, f_{phen_2_ETS}, f_{phen_3_ETS}, f_{phen_4_ETS}, f_{phen_5_ETS}$ are °C days (see Table A1.2; $f_{phen_1_ETS}$ and $f_{phen_5_ETS}$ define period crops to be sensitive to O₃ exposure),
 A_{start_ETS} and A_{end_ETS} are the start and the end of the accumulation period based on the effective temperature sums (counted from the day of the mid-anthesis for wheat and from the day of the tuber initiation for potato) above a base temperature of 0 °C for both wheat and potato at the start and end of the O₃ accumulation period; for POD₃IAM, see Table A1.4.

The parameter f_{O_3} in the case of wheat is calculated according to equation

$$f_{O_3} = [(1 + (POD_0/14)^8)]^{-1} \quad (A1.2d)$$

while $POD_0 = \sum_{n=A_{start}}^{H-1} F_{sto}(n) \cdot \frac{3600}{10^6}$ (A1.2e)

where POD_0 is the O₃ flux already accumulated since the beginning of the vegetation period A_{start} up to the last hour $H-1$,
 $F_{sto}(n)$ is the hourly O₃ flux in the hour n , calculated in the previous steps based on Equation 2.10, while $F_{sto}(A_{start})$ is equal to 0.

In the case of potato, the parameter (O₃ function) f_{O_3} is calculated according to equation

$$f_{O_3} = [(1+(AOTO/40)^5)^{-1}] \quad (A1.2f)$$

where $AOTO$ is accumulated O_3 concentration from the start of the vegetation period A_{start} up to the last hour $H-1$.

In the case of POD_3IAM , the parameter f_{O_3} is set to 1.

The parameter f_{light} is calculated according to

$$f_{light} = 1 - \text{EXP}[-light_a * \text{PPFD}] \quad (A1.2g)$$

$$\text{while } \text{PPFD} = \text{SSRD} * 0.5 * 4.5 \quad (A1.2h)$$

where $PPFD$ represents the photosynthetic photon flux density ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$ per second),
 $light_a$ is a light parameter (see Tables A1.3 and A1.4),
 $SSRD$ represents the surface net solar radiation in (W/m^2).

The parameter f_{temp} is calculated according to:

$$f_{temp} = \max \{f_{min}, [(T - T_{min}) / (T_{opt} - T_{min})] * [(T_{max} - T) / (T_{max} - T_{opt})]^{bt}\} \text{ when } T_{min} < T < T_{max} \\ = f_{min} \text{ when } T_{min} > T > T_{max} \quad (A1.2i)$$

$$\text{while } bt = (T_{max} - T_{opt}) / (T_{opt} - T_{min}) \quad (A1.2j)$$

where T_{min} , T_{max} and T_{opt} are minimum, maximum and optimum temperatures determining leaf stomata opening (see Tables A1.3 and A1.4)

The parameter f_{VPD} is calculated according to:

$$f_{VPD} = \min\{1, \max\{f_{min}, [(1-f_{min}) * (VPD_{min} - VPD) / (VPD_{min} - VPD_{max})] + f_{min}\}\} \quad (A1.2k)$$

$$\text{while } VPD = e_s(T_a) * (1-h_r) \quad (A1.2l)$$

$$e_s(T_a) = a \exp[bT_a / (T_a + c)] \quad (A1.2m)$$

where VPD_{min} is the minimum vapour pressure deficit determining leaf stomata opening (see Tables A1.3 and A1.4),
 VPD_{max} is the maximum vapour pressure deficit determining leaf stomata opening (see Tables A1.3 and A1.4),
 T_a is the air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
 h_r is the relative humidity (%) / 100,
 $e_s(T_a)$ is the potential (saturation) water vapour pressure,
 a, b, c are the empirical constants ($a = 0.611$ kPa, $b = 17.502$, $c = 240.97$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The ΣVPD (i.e. the function describing stomatal re-opening in the afternoon) is taken into account for maps POD_{SPEC} for wheat and potato. ΣVPD (kPa) should be calculated for daylight hours until dawn of the next day. If $\Sigma VPD \geq \Sigma VPD_{crit}$, g_{sto} calculated using Equation A1.2 is valid if smaller or equal to g_{sto} of the preceding hour. If g_{sto} is larger than g_{sto} of the preceding hour, given that ΣVPD is larger than or equal to ΣVPD_{crit} , it is replaced by the g_{sto} of the preceding hour.

The parameter f_{SW} is replaced by f_{SMI} (where SMI represents Soil Moisture Index with maximum at field capacity), taking values between 0 and 1 as a proportion of g_{max} (with 0 for soil moisture at and below

wilting point), following the parameterization given in Simpson et al. (2012), similar to the plant available water (PAW) parameterization f_{PAW} as defined for wheat in CLRTAP (2017a). The basic equation used for f_{SW} resp. f_{SMI} is:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{SMI} &= 0 && \text{for } SMI \leq 0 \\ &= \frac{SMI}{PAW_t} && \text{for } 0 < SMI \leq PAW_t \\ &= 1 && \text{for } SMI > PAW_t \end{aligned} \quad (A1.2n)$$

$$\text{while } SMI = \frac{SWLL - PWP}{FC - PWP} \quad (A1.2o)$$

where PAW_t is the threshold amount of water in the soil available to the plants, above which stomatal conductance is at a maximum, set to 0.5 (see Tables A1.3 and A1.4),
 $SWLL$ is the soil moisture in (m^3/m^3),
 PWP is the permanent wilting point in (cm^3/cm^3),
 FC is the field capacity in (cm^3/cm^3).

The Soil Moisture Index using the EMEP methodology as described in Simpson et al. (2012) and CLRTAP (2020) is used. It is computed using the soil moisture variable available from a meteorological model, which represents the water content in m^3 of water per m^3 of ground (m^3/m^3) in a specific ground level, in dependence on the available dataset. For soil moisture, the ECWMF's ERA5-Land variable Volume of water in soil layer 3 (i.e. 28-100 cm) has been used, see Annex 2, Section A2.1. The level of soil layer was chosen based on recommendation of Haberle and Svoboda (2015). The soil moisture is quite a sensitive parameter in the calculation of the POD. Next to the soil moisture, the soil moisture index also takes into account the permanent wilting point and the field capacity; they are taken from JRC soil database (JRC, 2016), see Annex 2, Section A2.1.

Modelling the hourly stomatal flux of ozone (F_{sto})

Once the hourly stomatal conductance of O_3 (g_{sto}) and all relevant variables are computed, the stomatal flux of O_3 (F_{sto}) can be calculated, based on the assumption that the concentration of O_3 at the top of the canopy represents a reasonable estimate of the concentration at the upper surface of the laminar layer for a sunlit upper canopy leaf. F_{sto} is calculated according to the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation) methodology, thus the fraction of the O_3 taken up by the stomata is given using a combination of the stomatal conductance, the quasi-laminar resistance and the leaf surface resistance (which depends on the external leaf, or cuticular, resistance). The hourly stomatal flux in the given hour H is calculated according to

$$F_{sto} = c(z_1) * g_{sto} * \frac{r_c}{r_b + r_c} \quad (A1.3)$$

where F_{sto} is the hourly stomatal flux of O_3 in ($nmol/m^2$ PLA per second)
 $c(z_1)$ is the concentration of O_3 at canopy top in ($nmol/m^3$)
 r_b is the quasi-laminar resistance in (s/m)
 r_c is the leaf surface resistance in (s/m)
 g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance in (m/s),

$$\text{while } r_c = 1/(g_{sto} + g_{ext}) \quad (A1.3a)$$

$$r_b = 1.3 * 150 * \sqrt{\frac{L}{u(z_1)}} \quad (A1.3b)$$

where g_{ext} is the external leaf, or cuticular, resistance in (m/s), equal to 1/2,500 m/s
 $u(z_1)$ is the wind speed at height z_1 (z_1 is the canopy top)
 L is the cross-wind leaf dimension (2 cm or 4 cm, see Tables A1.3 and A1.4)

while $u_{(z_1)} = \frac{u^*}{k} * \ln\left(\frac{z_1-d}{z_0}\right)$ for wheat
 $= \frac{u^*}{k} * \ln\left(\frac{z_1}{z_0}\right)$ for potato (A1.3c)

where k is the von Kármán constant (equal to 0.41)
 d is the displacement height usually assumed as 2/3 of the canopy height,
 z_1 is the top of the canopy
 z_0 is the roughness length usually assumed as 1/10 of the canopy height
 u^* is the friction velocity.

Box 3 Conversion of stomatal conductance g_{sto} and ozone concentration to units demanded for POD_Y calculation

Stomatal conductance g_{sto} has to be converted from units mmol/m^2 per second to units m/s (since all the resistances are expressed in the unit of s/m). At standard temperature ($20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and air pressure ($1.013 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$), the conversion is made by dividing the conductance in mmol/m^2 per second by 41,000 to give conductance in m/s .

To convert the **O_3 concentration (C)** at canopy height from $\mu\text{g/m}^3$ resp. ppb to nmol/m , the following equation should be used:

$$C (\text{nmol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}) = C (\text{ppb}) * P/(R\cdot T) = C (\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3) / 2 * P/(R\cdot T) \quad (\text{A1.4})$$

where P is the atmospheric pressure in Pa,
 R is the universal gas constant of $8.31447 \text{ J/mol per Kelvin}$
 T is the air temperature in Kelvin.

At standard temperature ($20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and air pressure ($1.013 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$), the concentration in ppb should be multiplied by 41.56 to calculate the concentration in nmol/m^3 .

Source: CLRTAP, 2024

Calculation of POD_Y from F_{sto}

Hourly averaged stomatal O_3 fluxes (F_{sto}) in excess of a Y threshold are accumulated over a species or vegetation-specific accumulation period using the following equation:

$$POD_Y = \sum_n (F_{sto}(n) - Y) \cdot \frac{3600}{10^6} \quad (\text{A1.5})$$

while $Y = 6 \text{ nmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA per second}$ (for $POD_{Y\text{SPEC}}$ for wheat or potato)
 $Y = 3 \text{ nmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA per second}$ (for $POD_{Y\text{IAM}}$)
 where POD_Y is the phytotoxic ozone dose related to the threshold Y , in ($\text{mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$),
 $F_{sto}(n)$ is the hourly ozone flux in the hour n of the accumulation period.

The value Y (in ($\text{nmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA per second}$)) is subtracted from each hourly averaged F_{sto} (in ($\text{nmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA per second}$)) value and the F_{sto} (after the subtracting of Y) is accumulated only when $F_{sto} > Y$, during daylight hours (when global radiation is more than 50 W/m^2). The value is then converted to hourly fluxes by multiplying by 3,600 and to mmol by dividing by 10^6 to get the stomatal ozone flux in $\text{mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$.

Critical levels of POD_Y

Table A1.2 shows critical levels (CLs) for crops as set by CLRTAP.

Table A1.2 POD₆SPEC and POD₃IAM critical levels (CL) for crops

Species	Effect parameter	Critical Levels (CL)	
		POD ₆ SPEC	POD ₃ IAM
Wheat	Grain yield	1.3	-
Wheat	1,000-grain weight	1.5	-
Wheat	Protein yield	2.0	-
Potato	Tuber yield	3.8	-
Crops	Grain yield	-	7.9

Source: CLRTAP, 2024.

A1.2 POD_Y parametrisation

Table A1.3 Parametrisation for POD₆SPEC for wheat flag leaves and the upper-canopy sunlit leaves of potato, for different biogeographical regions

Parameter	Units	(Bread) Wheat		Potato
		Atlantic, Boreal, Continental (<i>Pannonia, Steppic</i>)	Mediterranean	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental (<i>Mediterranean Pannonia, Steppic</i>)
g _{max}	mmol O ₃ /m ² PLA per second	500	430	750
f _{min}	fraction	0.01	0.01	0.01
light_a	-	0.0105	0.0105	0.005
T _{min}	°C	12	12	13
T _{opt}	°C	26	28	28
T _{max}	°C	40	39	39
VPD _{max}	kPa	1.2	3.2	2.1
VPD _{min}	kPa	3.2	4.6	3.5
ΣVPD _{crit}	kPa	8	16	10
PAW _t		0.5	0.5	0.5
f _{O3}	POD mmol O ₃ /m ² PLA per second	14	-	-
f _{O3}	AOT0, ppmh	-	-	40
f _{O3}	exponent	8	-	5
SGS	°C day	A _{start_ETS}	A _{start_ETS}	A _{start_ETS}
EGS	°C day	A _{end_ETS}	A _{end_ETS}	A _{end_ETS}
SGS _{length}	days	70	70	35
EGS _{length}	days	22	44	65
LAI _{min}	m ² /m ²	0	0	0
LAI _{max}	m ² /m ²	5	3.5	6
Leaf dimension	cm	2	2	4
Canopy height	m	1	0.75	1
f _{phen_a}	fraction	0.3	0.5	0.4
f _{phen_e}	fraction	0.7	0.5	0.2
f _{phen_1_ETS}	°C day	-200	-300	-330
f _{phen_2_ETS}	°C day	0	0	800
f _{phen_3_ETS}	°C day	100	70	-
f _{phen_4_ETS}	°C day	525	312	-
f _{phen_5_ETS}	°C day	700	550	-
mid-anthesis	°C day	1,075	1,250	-

Source: CLRTAP, 2024; González-Fernández et al., 2013; González-Fernández (personal communication, May 2021); Emberson et al., 2000b; Simpson et al., 2012.

Table A1.4 Parametrisation for POD₃IAM for flag leaves for crops, based on (bread) wheat

Parameter	Units	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonia, Steppic	Mediterranean
g_{max}	mmol O ₃ /m ² PLA per second	500	430
f_{min}	fraction	0.01	0.01
light_a	-	0.0105	0.0105
T _{min}	°C	12	13
T _{opt}	°C	26	28
T _{max}	°C	40	39
VPD _{max}	kPa	1.2	3.2
VPD _{min}	kPa	3.2	4.6
ΣVPD _{crit}	kPa	8	8
PAW _t		0.5	0.5
f_{O_3}	POD ₀ mmol O ₃ /m ² PLA per second	1	1
A _{start_ETS}	°C day	45 days before mid-anthesis*	45 days before mid-anthesis*
A _{end_ETS}	°C day	45 days after mid-anthesis*	45 days after mid-anthesis*
SGS	°C day	A _{start_ETS}	A _{start_ETS}
EGS	°C day	A _{end_ETS}	A _{end_ETS}
SGS _{length}	days	70	70
EGS _{length}	days	22	44
LAI _{min}	m ² /m ²	0	0
LAI _{max}	m ² /m ²	5	3.5
Leaf dimension	cm	2	2
Canopy height	m	1	1
f_{phen}		1	1
mid-anthesis	°C day	1,075	1,250

Notes: * 90d accumulation period, centred on the timing of mid-anthesis in wheat, see Section A1.1, Box 2 for details.

Source: CLRTAP, 2024; González-Fernández et al., 2013; González-Fernández (personal communication, May 2021); Emberson et al., 2000b; Simpson et al., 2012.

Map A1.1 Biogeographical regions in Europe

Source: EEA, 2016.

A1.3 Calculation of POD_γ spatial maps

Calculation of ozone spatial maps

The mapping method used is a linear regression model (using O₃ monitoring data from rural stations as a dependent variable and the chemical transport model results, altitude and solar radiation data as regressors) followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that model, according to the relation:

$$\hat{Z}(s_0) = c + a_1M(s_0) + a_2A(s_0) + a_3SSR(s_0) + \hat{R}(s_i) \quad (\text{A1.6})$$

where $\hat{Z}(s_0)$ is the estimated O₃ value at the point s_0 ,
 $M(s_0), A(s_0), SSR(s_0)$ are the chemical transport modelling (CTM), altitude and surface solar radiation values at the point s_0 ,
 c, a_1, a_2, a_3 are the parameters of the linear regression model calculated based on the O₃ monitoring and the supplementary data at the measurement points,
 $\hat{R}(s_i)$ is the spatial interpolation of the residuals of the linear regression model at the point s_0 calculated based on the residuals at the measurement points.

Ordinary kriging is used to interpolate the residuals:

$$\hat{R}(s_i) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i R(s_i), \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i = 1 \quad (\text{A1.6a})$$

where $R(s_i)$ are the residuals in the points of the measuring stations s_i ,
 $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_N$ are the weights estimated based on the variogram,
 N is the number of the stations used in the interpolation.

The variogram (as a measure of a spatial correlation) is estimated using a spherical function (with parameters nugget, sill, range). For details, see Horálek et al. (2007), Section 2.3.5 and Cressie (1993).

Calculation of POD_γ maps

During the POD_γ maps calculation, different biogeographical regions are considered. Plant stomatal functioning varies per plant species and can vary by biogeographical region, reflecting different adaptations of plants to climate and soil water in these regions. Parametrization for POD₆ (i.e. for wheat and potato) is currently available for all different biogeographic regions of Europe apart from Alpine region, i.e. for Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic, and Mediterranean regions (CLRTAP, 2017a). In the case of wheat, the parametrization is the same for most of these regions (namely Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, and Steppic), while for Mediterranean regions is different. For Alpine region, the parametrization of the Continental and several other regions are used. For potato, only one parametrization exists – it is set for all regions apart from the Alpine one. In the calculations, the existing parametrization has been applied for the entire mapping area.

The values calculated in 0.1° x 0.1° resolution were converted into the standard ETRS89-LAEA5210 projection and transferred into the EEA 2 km resolution grid.

A1.4 Calculation of vegetation exposure

Vegetation exposure for individual countries, large European regions, EU-27, EEA-32, EEA-38, and for the total mapping area is calculated based on the POD_γ maps in the 2 km resolution and either the land cover data in the 100 m resolution or agricultural data in 1 km resolution. For each POD_γ class, the total agricultural area per country and large region, as well as European-wide is determined.

In addition, the exposure for individual countries, large regions, EU-27, EEA-32, EEA-38 and the whole area is expressed also as the agricultural area weighted concentration, i.e. the average POD_Y value across the relevant agricultural area.

For the designation of the large regions, see Map A1.2. For details, see Horálek et al. (2024). Although the biogeographical regions (see Map A1.1) are more relevant in the context of POD_Y , the large European regions are used for consistency with the exposure estimates of other indicators, including AOT40.

Map A1.2 Five large European regions

Annex 2 Input data

A2.1 Data needed for calculation of POD_Y maps

Air quality monitoring data

Air quality station monitoring data for the relevant year as extracted from the official EEA Air Quality e-Reporting database, EEA (2024, 2025a) in March 2024 and February 2025 have been used. This data set has been supplemented with British stations from the Defra (2024, 2025) database ⁽⁴⁾ and with several EMEP rural stations from the EBAS (NILU, 2024, 2025) database not reported to the Air Quality e-Reporting database. Specifically, O_3 hourly values ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for all hours of the years 2022 and 2023 have been used.

Chemical transport modelling outputs

The CAMS Ensemble Forecast model outputs as provided by the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) at a regional scale over Europe have been used (CAMS, 2024), i.e. the ensemble of eleven involved air quality modelling outputs. Specifically, hourly O_3 values ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for all hours of the years 2022 and 2023 at a spatial resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ have been used. For details, see Horálek et al. (2024, 2025).

Meteorological parameters

The meteorological data used are the ECWMF data extracted from the CDS (Climate Data Store, <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/home>). Hourly data for 2022 and 2023 are used. Most of the data come from the reanalysed data set ERA5-Land at a $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ resolution (of CDS), namely the indicators:

Surface solar radiation (MW/m^2) – variable “Surface solar radiation downwards”,

Temperature (K) – variable “2m temperature”,

Surface pressure (Pa) – variable “surface_pressure”,

Soil water – variable “Volumetric soil water layer 3”, i.e. layer of 28-100 cm

Relative humidity – calculated based on variables “2m temperature” and “2m dewpoint temperature” (see below Eq. A1.7),

Wind speed (m/s) – calculated based on variables “10m u-component of wind” and “10m v-component of wind” (see below Eq. A1.8).

Relative humidity is derived by means of the saturated water vapour pressure (e_t) as a function of the indicators “2m temperature” (T) and “2m dew point temperature” (D) according to relation

$$RH = \frac{e_D}{e_T} = \frac{0.611 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot D}{240.97 + D}\right)}{0.611 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot T}{240.97 + T}\right)} = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot D}{240.97 + D}\right)}{\exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot T}{240.97 + T}\right)}, \quad (\text{A1.7})$$

where RH is the relative humidity,
 D is the dew point temperature at 2 meter height,
 T is the temperature at 2 meter height.

⁽⁴⁾ The United Kingdom exited the European Union in January 2020 and does not report air quality data to the AQ e-reporting database. Nevertheless, in order to enable the interpolation across the whole mapping domain, the publicly available British data from the Defra database have also been used in the analysis.

Wind speed (WV) is derived from the “10m u-component of wind” (10U) and “10m v-component of wind” (10V) according to relation

$$WV = \sqrt{(10U)^2 + (10V)^2} \quad (A1.8)$$

In the coastal areas (where the data from ERA5-Land are not available), the same parameters from the reanalysed data set ERA5 in 0.25°x0.25° resolution are applied. Next to this, the following data (not available in the ERA5-Land data set) from the ERA5 data set is also used:

Friction velocity (m/s) – variable “Friction velocity”. The friction velocity (also known as the shear-stress velocity) has the dimensions of velocity.

Surface sensible heat flux (W/m²) – variable “surface_sensible_heat_flux”.

Altitude

The altitude data field (in meters) of Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED2010) is used, with an original grid resolution of 15 arcseconds see Danielson and Gesch (2011). The data were re-gridded converted into the reference EEA 1 km resolution grid, see Horálek et al. (2024).

Soil hydraulic properties data

JRC data called "Maps of indicators of soil hydraulic properties for Europe" in 1 km resolution are used for POD calculations, JRC (2016). Namely the following indicators are used:

Wilting Point – water content at wilting point (cm³/cm³),
Field Capacity – water content at field capacity (cm³/cm³).

A2.2 Land cover data

CORINE Land Cover 2018 (CLC2018) – 100 m resolution, Version 2020_20 is used (EU, 2020). For areas missing in this database (i.e. Andorra, Jan Mayen and some border areas), MDA (2015) and ESA (2019) land cover data resampled to 100m resolution have been used. For details, see Horálek et al. (2024).

A2.3 Agricultural data

For determining the area covered by wheat and potato, the agricultural data for 2022 in 2 km resolution as applied in Schucht et al. (2024) have been used, i.e. the EUROSTAT wheat and potato production data spatialized from the NUTS-2 level to the 2 km grid resolution using the CLC2018 data of level-3 classes 2.1.1 “Non-irrigated arable land”, 2.4.1 “Annual crops associated with permanent crops”, 2.4.2 “Complex cultivation patterns”, and 2.4.3 “Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation”. For details, see Schucht et al. (2024).

Annex 3 Results of the POD_y analysis for biogeographical regions

This Annex 3 is related to Chapter 5. Similar results as presented in Chapter 5 at the country level (see Figures 5.2 to 5.8) are presented here at the level of the biogeographical regions.

Figure A3.1 (related to Figures 5.2 to 5.6 showing results for countries) presents the inter-annual differences between years 2022 and 2023 for POD_{3_ref} and the different contributions of the limitation functions. Figures A3.2 and A3.3 (related to Figures 5.7 to 5.8 presenting results for countries) show heatmaps of POD_{3_ref} and heatmaps of the different contributions of the limitation functions for years 2022 and 2023.

Figure A3.1 POD_{3_ref} Inter-annual variation 2023-2022 of POD_{3_ref} for wheat in mmol/m² (left) and efficiency of the limitation functions for its reduction in % (right), biogeographical regions, in mmol/m² PLA

Figure A3.2 POD₃_ref for wheat in mmol/m² PLA (left) and efficiency of the limitation functions for its reduction in % (right) in 2022 for biogeographical regions

Figure A3.3 POD₃_ref for wheat in mmol/m² PLA (left) and efficiency of the limitation functions for its reduction in % (right) in 2023 for biogeographical regions

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